

**HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS INFECTION AND VACCINATION: KNOWLEDGE,
ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE AMONG FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES OF THE
UNIVERSITY OF BENIN**

BY

SAMSON AZIEGBEMHIN MOMOH

MED1404712

CHIDINMA NDUBUISI

MED1404713

**DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNITY HEALTH, SCHOOL OF MEDICINE,
COLLEGE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES,
UNIVERSITY OF BENIN, BENIN CITY, EDO STATE, NIGERIA**

JUNE, 2023

**HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS INFECTION AND VACCINATION: KNOWLEDGE,
ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE AMONG FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES OF THE
UNIVERSITY OF BENIN**

BY

SAMSON AZIEGBEMHIN MOMOH

MED1404712

CHIDINMA NDUBUISI

MED1404713

**A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNITY HEALTH,
SCHOOL OF MEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF BENIN, IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT
OF THE AWARD OF THE BACHELOR OF MEDICINE AND BACHELOR OF
SURGERY (MBBS) DEGREE OF THE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN**

JUNE, 2023

DECLARATION

We hereby declare that this study is original and was carried out under the supervision of Prof. Omokhoa Adeleye and has not been published anywhere else for the award of a degree, certificate or for any other purpose.

SAMSON AZIEGBEMHIN MOMOH
MED1404712
08131832460
samson.momoh@med.uniben.edu

CHIDINMA NDUBUISI
MED1404713
07062558696
chidinmandubuisi001@gmail.com

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research study titled **“HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS INFECTION AND VACCINATION: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE AMONG FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES OF THE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN”** was carried out by **SAMSON AZIEGBEMHIN MOMOH** with matriculation number **MED1404712** and **CHIDINMA NDUBUISI** with matriculation number **MED1404713** under supervision in the Department of Community Health, College of Medical Sciences , University of Benin as part of the requirement for the award of Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery (MBBS).

PROF. OMOKHOA ADELEYE
PROJECT SUPERVISOR
MBBS, MHPM, MPH, MSc, FWACP
Professor/Consultant
Department of Community
Health,
School of Medicine,
University of Benin,
Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

DR. ANDREW OBI
AG. HEAD OF DEPARTMENT
MBBS, MPH, FMCPH
Senior Lecturer/Consultant
Department of Community
Health
School of Medicine,
University of Benin,
Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to our respective families and loved ones whose steadfast love and support brought us thus far and to all our esteemed teachers who taught and guided us through the years.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are grateful to the Department of Community Health, School of Medicine, University of Benin for giving us the opportunity to carry out this research. We wish to express our special gratitude to our supervisor, Prof. O.A. Adeleye for his kindness, sacrifice, patience, guidance and support in the supervision of our project.

I am grateful to all those who helped me in one way or the other to get to this point in life. To my mother, Mrs. Clara Momoh, thank you for your love and untold sacrifice over the years. I will not forget to thank my uncles, Rev. Dr. Augustine Momoh and Mr Azorbor Odumu; my sister, Miss Sarah Momoh; my cousins, Innocent Amondu and Engr. Williams Amondu and my benefactor, Engr. Dr. E.J.S Uujamhan. Without you all, I will not be here. Special thanks to my project partner, Chidinma Ndubusi and all the other great friends who helped me survive this programme.

Samson Aziembemhin Momoh

I am grateful to my family: my father, Rev. Ndubuisi Nwauba; my mother, Mrs. Victoria Ndubuisi; and my brother, Okwuchukwu Ndubuisi, for their unwavering support. I appreciate my project partner, Samson Momoh, whose collaboration and shared enthusiasm was indispensable to the completion of this project. Special thanks to my roommate, Jessica Iyoha for always being ready to listen whenever I started to talk about this project. To my friends: Richard Adejumola, Afoke Asah, Ese Emmanuel, Emmanuel Onowaro and Segun Adams, “I am, because we are, and since we are, therefore I am”.

Chidinma Ndubuisi

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title page	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ii
Declaration	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	iii
Certification	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	iv
Dedication	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	v
Acknowledgement	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	vi
Table of contents	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	vii
List of tables	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	viii
List of figures	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ix
List of abbreviation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
Definition of terms	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	xi
Abstract	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	xii
Chapter One: Introduction	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Chapter Two: Literature review	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7
Chapter Three: Materials and Methods	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17
Chapter Four: Results	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	30
Chapter Five: Discussion	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	64
Conclusion	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	71
Recommendations	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	72
References	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	74
Appendices	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	81

LIST OF TABLES

- Table 1: List of faculties/school and the number of female undergraduates and mid-level female undergraduates
- Table 2: List of faculties/school and the number of selected respondents
- Table 3: Selected degree programs
- Table 4: Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents
- Table 5: Respondents knowledge of HPV infection
- Table 6: Determinants of knowledge of HPV infection
- Table 7: Respondents' practice regarding HPV infection
- Table 8: Respondents' knowledge of HPV vaccination
- Table 9: Determinants of respondent's knowledge of HPV vaccination
- Table 10: Respondents' attitude towards HPV vaccination
- Table 11: Score of respondents' attitudes towards HPV vaccination
- Table 12: Determinants of respondents' attitude towards HPV vaccination
- Table 13: Respondents' HPV vaccination uptake (vaccination status)
- Table 14: Reasons for vaccination and non-vaccination
- Table 15: Factors associated with respondents' vaccination status

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1: A pie chart showing the respondents' knowledge of infection
- Figure 2: A pie chart showing the respondents' knowledge of HPV vaccination
- Figure 3: A pie chart showing the respondents' attitude towards HPV vaccination
- Figure 4: A pie chart showing the number of respondents' uptake of HPV vaccination

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

COVID-19:	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CSO:	Civil Society Organization
DNA:	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
FMoH:	Federal Ministry of Health
HIV:	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HPV:	Human Papillomavirus
NDHS:	Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey
NHIS:	National Health Insurance Scheme
NPI:	National Program on Immunization
NUC:	National University Commission
STIs:	Sexually Transmitted Infections
WHO:	World Health Organization

DEFINITION OF TERMS

ADOLESCENT: Individuals within the 10-19 years age group.

INFECTION: The invasion and growth of germs in the body.

SEXUAL DEBUT: The age at which people have sexual intercourse for the first time in their lifetime.

SEXUAL INTERCOURSE: Sexual contact between individuals involving penetration, especially the insertion of a man's erect penis into a woman's vagina, typically culminating in orgasm and the ejaculation of semen.

VACCINE: A product that stimulates a person's immune system to produce immunity to a specific disease

VACCINATION: The act of introducing a vaccine into the body to produce immunity to a specific disease.

ABSTRACT

Background: Human Papillomavirus (HPV) infection is a significant global health issue responsible for several life-threatening diseases like cervical cancer, vulva cancer, penile cancer etc. It disproportionately affects young women in whom it causes cervical cancer – the worst and most common sequelae of the infection. Safe sexual practices and HPV vaccine are the main protective measures against the infection, the latter being more emphasized globally as the best means to get protected against the infection and its associated diseases.

Objectives: This study sought to assess the knowledge and practice regarding HPV infection, evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and uptake regarding HPV vaccination, and determine the reasons for vaccination status among mid-level female undergraduates of the University of Benin.

Method: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted using a convenience sampling method. Respondents were selected across all faculties in UNIBEN and data were collected using structured self-administered questionnaire. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Version 25.0. The study was carried out between 2021 and 2023.

Result: Four hundred and four mid-level female undergraduates participated in this study. The mean age of the respondents was 21.00 ± 1.98 years. Two hundred and seventy-six (68.9%) had had sex and the mean age of sexual debut was 16.87 ± 3.6 years, 137 (49.6%) had 1 – 2 sexual partners and 182 (65.9%) had ever used a condom. Only 157 (39.0%) and 103 (25.0%) of the students had good knowledge of HPV infection and HPV vaccines respectively. While 137 (34.0%) had a positive attitude towards HPV vaccination, only 7 (1.7%) had received at least one dose of the vaccine. Bioscience course, increase in the age and class were associated with better knowledge of HPV infection. These associations were also observed in knowledge of HPV vaccination.

Conclusion: The findings showed an overall poor knowledge of HPV infection and vaccination. Vaccine uptake was very low. Attitude towards HPV vaccination was poor. Increased awareness and addressing identified barriers to vaccination are possible solutions to these problems.

Key words: Human papillomavirus, infection, vaccine, undergraduates.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Epidemiological research over the last decade has demonstrated that human papillomavirus (HPV) is the most widespread and common sexually transmitted infections worldwide.¹ It has been estimated that more than 80% of sexually active women and men will contract at least one HPV infection by the age of 45 years.^{1,2} However, most of them will be transient infections without any clinical impact. In women, 90% of the incident HPV genital infections will clear within two years but persistence of these infections will result in cervical cancer.¹⁻³ HPV is the only known cause of cervical cancer with a prevalence of 99.7% in all cases of cervical cancer.⁴

HPV is a circular, double-stranded DNA virus that is believed to have co-diverged with animal and human host populations for millions of years and are ubiquitous. HPV infect basal epithelial cells, causing benign and malignant lesions of the skin and mucosae of the anogenital and upper aero-digestive tract.^{5,6} There are over 200 types of HPV, which are classified into low- and high-risk types. The low-risk types, such as HPV 6 and 11, cause 90% of anogenital warts, and also respiratory papillomatosis, a potentially deadly disease. The high-risk types, such as HPV 16, 18, 31, 33 and 45 cause most cervical cancers as well as cancers of the anus, vulva, vagina, penis, and oropharynx. Among the high-risk types, HPV types 16 and 18 cause 70% of cervical cancers worldwide.^{7,8}

The peak time for acquiring infection for both women and men is shortly after becoming sexually active. HPV is sexually transmitted, but penetrative sex is not required for transmission. Skin-to-skin genital contact is a well-recognized mode of transmission.² Following the identification of the role of HPV in the aetiology of cervical cancer, four prophylactic vaccines targeting various high-risk HPV types have been developed. The monovalent vaccine (HPV16), the bivalent vaccine (Cervarix which protects against HPV 16 and 18), the quadrivalent vaccine

(Gardasil which protects against HPV 16, 18, 6 and 11) and more recently, the nonavalent vaccine (Gardasil-9 which protects against HPV 16, 18, 6, 11, 31, 33, 45, 52 and 58). The bivalent and quadrivalent vaccines were licensed for use in 2006/2007 and even over this relatively short period the beneficial effects of the vaccine are already evident; with decreases in the incidence of high-grade cervical abnormalities, the prevalence of vaccine HPV types and the incidence of genital warts in some developed countries.⁴ Vaccines against HPV have been available since 2006 and recommended by World Health Organization (WHO) since 2009.⁹

Since first licensure of human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccines in 2006, the HPV vaccines (bivalent, quadrivalent and nonavalent) have proven to be safe and able to induce strong direct and indirect protection against HPV and its sequelae. National programs with just 50% coverage (or more) of 2 or 3 dose schedules have demonstrated a dramatic impact on population level HPV prevalence, persistent HPV infection, genital warts, and cervical intraepithelial neoplasia.^{2,10}

HPV vaccines work best if administered prior to exposure to HPV. Therefore, the WHO recommends to vaccinate girls aged between 9 and 14 years, when most have not started sexual activity.¹¹ According to the Nigeria Demographic Health Survey (NDHS) done in 2018, the median age of first sexual debut among women is 17.2 years (a slight decrease from 17.6 years in 2013), while the median age among men is 21.7 years. On average, women initiate sexual intercourse 4.5 years earlier than men.¹² The vaccines cannot treat HPV infection or HPV-associated disease, such as cancer. Some countries have started to vaccinate boys as the vaccination prevents genital cancers in males as well as in females.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In Nigeria different HPV infection prevalence have been reported which ranged from 10% in Port Harcourt (Kennedy et al, 2016), 26.3 % in Ibadan (Thomas et al, 2004) to 37% in Abuja (Akarolo-Anthony et al, 2014). The prevalence of HPV infection in these studies was high compared to the adjusted global HPV prevalence of 11.7% in a previous study done by Bruni et al, 2010. This high prevalence rate is an indication of continuous transmission of the infection and hence the importance of implementation of measures for the control of the spread of the virus and its resultant sequelae in Nigeria.¹³

Cervical cancer is by far the most common life-threatening HPV-related disease. Nearly all cases of cervical cancer can be attributed to HPV infection.² It has been reported that more than 99% of cervical cancer is associated with high risk HPV genital infection.^{4,14} Nigeria has a population of 56.2 million women ages 15 years and older who are at risk of developing cervical cancer with a national standardized prevalence rate of 33.0 per 100,000. Current estimates indicate that every year, 12,075 women are diagnosed with cervical cancer and 7,968 die from the disease. Cervical cancer ranks as the 2nd most frequent cancer among women in Nigeria after breast cancer.¹⁵ Cervical cancer is a disease of great public health interest because it is easily preventable and primarily affects women aged 15 – 44 years, an age group within which women make great social and economic contributions.¹⁶

The devastating situation of cervical cancer in Nigeria is not limited to the high incidence and mortality rate of the disease, but also of greater concern is low level of awareness of ways to prevent a woman from having cervical cancer which could be through primary prevention by the human papillomavirus vaccine.¹⁷ Despite the prevalence and burden of cervical cancer worldwide with almost 80% occurring in developing countries such as Nigeria, only about 52% of Nigerian women were aware of this deadly disease.¹⁸ This is quite critical because of limited infrastructure

for effective treatment for invasive cervical cancer particularly when diagnosed in late stages.¹⁷ In addition, the situation where majority of citizens have no health insurance coverage, even among the few with health insurance coverage, screening for cervical cancer and HPV vaccine are not covered by the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS).¹⁹ Although the WHO recommends to vaccinate girls aged between 9 and 14 years, when most have not started sexual activity, several studies that has been done across the country has shown that the awareness and uptake of HPV vaccines is low (19.7% and 25.3%) and this is a cause for concern.¹¹ The reasons for this may not be far-fetched considering the high poverty level (48.4%) in Nigeria.²⁰ Out-of-pocket payment for vaccination which cost about 40,000 – 60,000 Naira is a great deal of money to part with. Asides cost, a presumed lack of awareness and poor risk perception among even educated population with access to information on the internet seems to be a major deterring factor in the demand for HPV vaccination. Hence, this research aims to assess the level of awareness of HPV and to determine the reasons for vaccination and non-vaccination among female students of the University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

HPV vaccination is the best method to prevent and possibly eradicate cervical cancer. Considering the mortality and morbidity associated with cervical cancer, as well as its high socio-economic burden, the need for prevention through HPV vaccination cannot be overemphasized. This is particularly important for developing countries like Nigeria where screening services are low, thereby most patients present in the late stages of cervical cancer, which makes survival rate low and the cost of care high. Also, the age of onset of first sexual debut among teenagers is increasingly getting lower and the later part of this age group make up a good proportion of those offered admissions into tertiary institution. The freedom that comes with finally being out of their parent's supervision is associated with increased chances of sexual intercourse. Combined with the fact that most of these sexual activities are unprotected and sexual partners are most time multiple,

the rate of HPV infection will continue to increase and the resultant cervical cancer it causes will reciprocally continue to rise in the future.

Notwithstanding the potential benefits of HPV vaccination, there seems to be low concrete effort to ensure that all eligible individuals are vaccinated, as evidenced by HPV vaccination not being included among the routine vaccine in the National Program on Immunization (NPI) Schedule.

This study will help to find out the current level of awareness of HPV infection and vaccination among the study population. It will also help to determine the reasons for vaccination status among the study population. This will add to the pool of knowledge on the subject matter. And will be useful to policy makers in making necessary health policies regarding HPV awareness, vaccination and promotion of safe sexual practices.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following questions are central to this research which will be carried out among female undergraduate students of the University of Benin.

1. What is the level of knowledge, practice and determinants regarding HPV infection?
2. What is the level of knowledge, attitude and uptake of HPV vaccines?
3. What are the reasons for vaccination and non-vaccination?
4. What are the factors associated with vaccination status?

1.5 OBJECTIVES

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To assess the knowledge, attitude and practice regarding HPV infection and vaccination and to identify the reasons for HPV vaccination status among female undergraduates of the University of Benin.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

The following specific objectives will be assessed among female undergraduate students of the University of Benin.

1. To assess the knowledge, practice and determinants regarding HPV infection
2. To assess the knowledge, attitude and uptake regarding HPV vaccination.
3. To identify reasons for HPV vaccination status.
4. To determine factors associated with HPV vaccine uptake.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

University students and young adults have a high prevalence of genital HPV infection because of their risky sexual behavior, lack of knowledge of HPV infection and HPV-related diseases, and misconceptions about susceptibility.²¹ In the NDHS 2018 survey, overall, more than half of women and men age 15 - 49 (58% and 54% respectively) reported having sexual intercourse during the four weeks before the survey.¹²

HPV vaccines are now available and have the potential to reduce the incidence of cervical cancer. Achieving a 70% coverage, HPV vaccine can prevent more than four million deaths in women in low-income to middle-income countries over the next decade. Three prophylactic HPV vaccines are currently available: bivalent, quadrivalent and nonavalent. The vaccine may be given as early as 9 years of age through 26 years of age. Vaccinating >80% of girls reduces the risk of HPV infection in boys. Therefore, countries are recommended to prioritize vaccinations for girls aged 9–14 years, while women aged >15 years and men should be grouped as secondary target. A two-dose schedule is recommended for age <15 years, and a three-dose schedule is recommended for age >15 years.²²

The vaccines have been found 70–100% effective in preventing cervical cancer. The vaccines were licensed and introduced in Nigeria in 2009, uptake has ranged between 0 and 49% being utilized by only a few privileged populations. The knowledge of HPV infections and HPV vaccines, among the Nigeria population, is inadequate, and the cost of HPV vaccination per person is beyond what the average Nigerian can afford. Awareness and knowledge of the infections and the vaccines will stimulate demand and uptake of the vaccines. Increasing demand may drive the introduction of the vaccine into the national immunization schedule thereby making the vaccine more affordable and accessible.²³

2.1 KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICE REGARDING HPV INFECTION

A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Kingdom of Bahrain, in February 2018, among attendees of primary healthcare centers. Of the 408 people interviewed, only 13.5% (55) had heard of HPV infection, with the media being the most common source of knowledge (45.5%, n=25). The two variables, which had a significant association with awareness of HPV, were female gender and employment in the health sector (p-value < 0.001 for both). Out of those who had heard of HPV, 39 (70.9%) identified HPV to be a sexually transmitted infection. When asked if both men and women were infected by the virus, the majority (80%, n = 44) answered correctly. Sixty-nine per cent (n = 38) knew that the persistence of the virus can lead to cervical cancer and that unsafe sexual practices can increase the probability of getting HPV infection, while 60% (n = 33) were aware that HPV may lead to other genital cancers. More than two-thirds of the people (72.7%, n = 40) believed that prevention against the virus can prevent cervical cancer as well. A cluster multistage sampling method and an interview-based questionnaire was used in the study.²⁴

In a cross-sectional descriptive study conducted at the University of Lagos between 30th of May and 29th of July 2010, of the 398 participants, 214 (56.4%) were aware of cervical cancer, 64 (17.7%) were aware of HPV infection. The minimum sample size was calculated using a finite population and adjusted for anticipated non-response by 10%. Assuming 50% of the formula students had sufficient knowledge about HPV infection, a random sample of 398 female undergraduate students were selected using a two-stage sampling technique with 95% confidence and 5% reliability. The faculties in the university were considered as the primary sampling units. The faculty of Education and the faculty of Social Sciences were selected and the study participants were then selected from a sample frame of full-time, undergraduate, female students from these two faculties using the simple random sampling technique.²¹

Another study conducted between 2013 to 2014 in Oyo and Osun States found the level of awareness of HPV infection to be low. One hundred and seventy-six (23.9%) of the 737

respondents had good knowledge of HPV. This was a questionnaire-based cross-sectional survey carried out in Oyo and Osun States in southwestern Nigeria. The study population included randomly selected women aged 18 years and above as at the time of the administration of questionnaire. Face-to-face structured interviews were conducted after the purpose of the study had been explained to the participants and their informed consent sought and gained. Women who did not give their consent were excluded from this study.²⁵

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among female medical and dental students of the University of Benin and reported in 2016. Of the 215 participants, one hundred and eighty-three respondents (85.1%) had heard of human papillomavirus. Their source of information was mainly from school lectures 148 (78.7%). All of the respondents (100.0%) had heard of cervical cancer and their source of information was also mainly from school lectures 144 (67.0%). One hundred and eighteen (91.8%), 116 (63.4%) and 54 (29.5%) of the respondents had a correct knowledge that HPV causes cancer of the cervix, can cause genital warts and cannot cause herpes respectively. Quantitative method of data collection was utilized with the aid of pretested semi-structured, self-administered questionnaires.²²

In another study conducted in 2014 among 408 participants in Ankara, Turkey, the most frequently listed method of prevention of HPV infection among young women was the use of condoms (24.8%); however, hygiene seemed to be important in the prevention of HPV among the adolescents (26.7%, $p = 0.002$). Vaccination was mentioned by less than 15% in both groups, and screening was regarded as the least popular choice in both groups (Less than 2%).²⁶ Self-administered questionnaires were used in the study. However, the study type as well as sample determination method used in the research was not stated. Therefore, the result is not reliable.

A study was conducted among full-time female undergraduate students in Rivers State in 2015. Among the seven hundred and eighty respondents, two hundred and sixty-two (33.6%) of the students had heard of HPV infection. Among the students who had heard of HPV infection, 182

(69.4%) were aware that the infection could be sexually transmitted and 133 (50.8%) were aware that the infection could cause cervical cancer. Most of the students (92.7%) who had heard of HPV infection knew at least one risk factor for the infection. Respondents listed multiple sex partners, 117 (44.7%) and sexual debut before 18 years of age, 36 (13.7%), as the top risk factors for HPV infection. It was a descriptive cross-sectional study carried out between July and October 2015 in three universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. Multistage sampling was used to identify the study participants.²⁷

2.2 KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND UPTAKE OF HPV VACCINATION

Primary protection against HPV is gotten by prophylactic vaccination. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends routine vaccination of girls 9-13 years of age because they are not as likely to have begun sexual activity but human papillomavirus vaccination still lags behind other vaccination types both in developed and developing countries.²⁸ The effectiveness of a vaccine delivery program depends largely upon the awareness of the vaccine and the attitude in terms of acceptability of the vaccine.²⁵

A study was done to provide a detailed characterization of human papillomavirus vaccine awareness, knowledge and information sources in the HPV vaccine decision-making process of youth, both male and female, in Switzerland. Quantitative questionnaires and qualitative interviews were used. The study participants were 15-26 years of age. The questionnaires were administered to 997 youths (585 male, 412 female). Of the total participants, 697 (70%) participants were knowledgeable about the HPV vaccine. Females were more likely to be knowledgeable than males (342/412 (83%) vs 355/585 (61%); $p < 0.01$).²⁹

A cross-sectional study was conducted among students of the Faculty of Health Sciences at a private university in Mogadishu, Somalia, between January to March 2021. The sample consisted of a total of 220 female undergraduate students. The data of the study were collected using a

questionnaire consisting 32 questions evaluating the knowledge and attitudes of the students about cervical cancer, HPV and HPV vaccine. The results showed that 159 (72.3%) had neither heard of HPV vaccine nor knew that HPV vaccine is protective against cervical cancer.³⁰

A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out between July 2015 and October 2015 in three universities in Rivers State, Port Harcourt. This study aimed to assess the level of awareness of HPV infection and vaccine uptake among female university students. Multistage sampling was used to identify the study participants. Among the study participants who had heard of HPV vaccine, 148 (72.9%) were aware that the vaccine could protect against HPV infection and 97 (12.4%) were aware that the vaccine could protect against cervical cancer. A total of 165 (81.3%) participants were aware that the vaccine is available in Nigeria. Only 40 (5.1%) of the students had received at least one dose of HPV vaccine.²⁷

A study was done from February 2019 to April 2019 to evaluate the knowledge, attitude and acceptability of HPV vaccine and vaccination among university students in Indonesia. A total of 433 students from medical, nursing, social sciences and other faculties participated in the survey. Self-administered online questionnaire was used. Attitudes toward the HPV vaccine and vaccination in general was positive. Over 70% of the participants believed that the HPV vaccine is safe and highly effective. However, around 21% of the participants tend to agree that vaccination is not required for healthy individuals. Of 226 respondents, 143 (63.3%) pointed out that there is a risk of HPV infection even at an early age of 9-14 years old. Of 226 students, 204 (90.3%) stressed that HPV vaccination should be integrated into the national immunization program in the future.³¹

A cross-sectional study was conducted among female high-school students in Jimma town, Ethiopia from May 13 through September 10, 2021. A total of 366 students participated in this study with a response rate of 94.8%. Most of the respondents 277 (75.7%) were of the opinion that if they feel at risk of getting HPV, they will take the vaccine. Other findings showed that 246 (67.2%) of the respondents were of the opinion that being infected with HPV is very deadly and

can lead to death, 265 (72.4%) of the respondents thought that by taking the vaccine, they would be safe and healthy, and 127 (34.7%) said that their parents must be the ones to decide for them.³²

A descriptive cross-sectional survey to assess the knowledge, attitude and uptake of human papillomavirus vaccination was conducted among 400 female undergraduates of Lagos State Polytechnic in August 2018. Participants were selected using a multi-stage sampling technique and data was collected with a pretested, self-administered, semi-structured questionnaire. In general, majority (92.7%) of the respondents had positive attitude towards the uptake of HPV vaccine. Over two-third (69.8%) of the respondents agreed to the statement: “HPV vaccination should be included in the National Program on Immunization”, while less than a third (27.4%) agreed to the statement “HPV vaccine may have long negative effects on me”.³³

Coverage data are of paramount importance to correctly interpret measures of the vaccine’s impact especially given that reduction in cervical cancer incidence cannot be detected for many years after the vaccine has been introduced in a country.

In a cross-sectional study done in China, 1,029 college students living in mainland China were recruited through convenience sampling between December 2018 and March 2019 and the link to an online questionnaire was sent. After excluding seven questionnaires owing to incomplete responses, the data of 1,022 participants were analyzed. The mean age of the sample, which included 267 (26.1%) males and 755 (73.9%) females, was 20.35 ± 3.49 years. Of the final sample, only 3.1% had been vaccinated against HPV, including 5 males and 27 females.³⁴

A study was carried out in 2020 in Uganda with the aim of determining the prevalence of HPV vaccine uptake and associated factors among 10 to 17-year-old girls in Central Uganda four years after rolling out the vaccine in the country. The cross-sectional survey was done in Wakiso and Nakasongola districts in Central Uganda. A total of 503 girls participated in the study. The results

of this study indicated that HPV vaccine uptake in Central Uganda among girls aged 10 to 17 years was low (39.4%) compared to the 2015 Uganda's ministry of health's target of 80%.³⁵

A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among 384 students of Lagos State College of Science and Technology (LASPOTTECH) in October 2018. Of the 384 respondents, only ten (2.6%) of the respondents had received HPV vaccine, out of which 60% completed the vaccine doses. A multistage sampling method was employed to select female undergraduates (aged 15–24 years), a survey questionnaire (semi-structured, self-administered) which was adapted from a review of relevant literatures was administered. Data collected was entered into and analyzed using IBM SPSS version 20 statistical package.³³

An institution-based cross-sectional study was carried out in 2021 to assess the knowledge of human papillomavirus and uptake of its vaccine among female undergraduate students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria. Two hundred and twenty-nine students were selected using multi-staged sampling technique. The result showed that only 1 (0.44%) student had received the vaccine.³⁶

2.3 REASONS FOR HPV VACCINATION STATUS

A study done in 2013 which was aimed at determining HPV vaccine uptake (≥ 1 dose) among adolescent girls in Hong Kong, China, and to explore the reasons for non-acceptance of the vaccine had a total of 1832 secondary school girls (15.5 ± 2.0 years) who were randomly surveyed. Their HPV vaccine uptake was estimated, and their reasons for non-vaccination summarized. Amongst the 1689 non-vaccinated girls, 1587 (94.0%) reported one or more reasons for not having received the HPV vaccine. The top five reasons were 'never heard of the vaccine or know little about it' (20.6%), 'do not know where to receive it' (20.2%), 'too expensive' (17.8%), 'have concerns about its efficiency and safety' (12.4%) and 'concerned about the age for vaccination' (6.5%).

Misperceptions of the HPV infection risk were also prevalent, with 5.9% considering it to have little to do with them and 6.5% believing adolescence was too early to receive the vaccine. Parent-related reasons, including a lack of initiation from parents and parental objections, were reported by 5.6% of the non-vaccinated girls.³⁷

In the previously cited cross-sectional study conducted among students of the Faculty of Health Sciences at a private university in Mogadishu, Somalia, between January to March 2021. Of the total participants none had received the HPV vaccine. Majority (72.3%) of them stated lack of information as reason for non-vaccination, while 71.4% stated that they did not know that the HPV vaccine protects against cervical cancer. The absence of a widespread HPV vaccination program in Somalia is one of the main causes. Given the lack of knowledge and awareness, the expense and cost of the vaccine appears to be the main deterrent to vaccination.³⁰

Another study in 2019 which utilized a descriptive cross-sectional survey design was conducted among 240 female undergraduates of Obafemi Awolowo University. The data was collected using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire. Findings from the survey revealed the highest proportion of the respondents (49.2%) were aged between 15–20 years, 32.9% were in their 200 level. The key reasons identified for low uptake of HPV vaccination were inadequate information about HPV vaccines (96.7%). However, the least identified factor for low uptake of the primary preventive measures was some of the respondents considered their age too young to receive HPV vaccines (15%)³⁸.

2.4 FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH HPV VACCINE UPTAKE

Several factors influence the acceptability and uptake of HPV vaccination in countries where there is no organized cervical cancer prevention program. Some of them were highlighted in the research works reported below.

In an online survey conducted in 2018 in the United States of America, participants were recruited from a metropolitan research university in Jefferson County, Kentucky, with an undergraduate enrollment of more than 16,000 students. Of the 645 surveys initiated, 585 completed more than 95% of the questions. The majority of the respondents were female (78%), white (74%), and heterosexual (90%), who had 1–2 lifetime sexual partners (36%). The results of this study showed that knowledge in limited areas did predict vaccine uptake. Specifically, those who correctly answered that finger and genital warts were from different HPV types were twice as likely to be HPV vaccinated (aOR 2.05 (1.08, 3.91)); and those who incorrectly categorized plantar warts as caused by HPV were significantly less likely to be vaccinated. Significant influencers to being vaccinated were reduced to only parent/guardian influence in the multivariate model (aOR 5.32 (2.17, 13.03) with the opportunity for shared choice or the doctor's recommendation becoming not significant.³⁹

The results of a cross-sectional population-based survey done in two (one urban and one rural) of the 27 districts in Central Uganda for a duration of two months (June to July 2019), showed that the likelihood of vaccination was higher among girls whose mothers had high knowledge about HPV vaccination compared to girls whose mothers had low knowledge, indicating a positive effect of high mothers' knowledge about HPV vaccination on HPV vaccination uptake. The study also found that schooling girls were more likely to have been vaccinated compared to non-schooling girls. The probable explanation for this relationship is the use of the school-based HPV vaccine delivery scheme minus special effort to vaccinate girls who were not schooling.³⁵

In 2019, a cross-sectional study design was employed and stratified sampling technique used to recruit 310 consenting students in Bowen University Teaching Hospital, Ogbomosho, Nigeria. A pre-tested self-administered, semi-structured questionnaire was used for data collection. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were carried out. The result of this study showed that 79.4% knew that the vaccine is available in the country but 53.2% did not know where to obtain it. At the multivariate level, the odds of getting vaccinated was significantly higher among female respondents compared to their male counterparts (OR=1.56;95%CI=1.26-1.31). The odds of HPV vaccination were also significantly higher among those who demonstrated positive attitude compared to those with negative attitude (OR=1.16; 95%CI=0.11-0.22). Moreover, respondents who had had sex without using condom were significantly more likely to have been vaccinated against HPV compared to others (OR;0.19, 95%CI; 0.45-0.85)⁴⁰.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 STUDY AREA

This study was conducted in the University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. Edo State is one of the 36 states in Nigeria, its capital is Benin City, it is located in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The state was created in 1991 from the northern portion of the defunct Bendel State and has a land mass of 19, 743sq/km. The state lies geographically between latitudes 6°23'55"N to 6°27'39"N and 5°36'18"E to 5°44'18"E and has its boundaries with Ondo State to the west, Anambra State to the east, Kogi State to the north-east and Delta State to the south-east. The state consists of closely related ethnic groups like Benin, Esan, Etsako, Owan, as well as a pool of smaller tribes which reside in the state. Edo State has a total of seven universities. It has one federal university, two state universities and four privately owned universities.⁴¹

Benin City, an ancient metropolis is the capital and seat of government of Edo State. It is bounded by latitude 6° 06'N, 6° 30'N and longitude 5° 30'E, 5° 45'E of the Greenwich meridian. It occupies land area of 500 square kilometers, situated 200 miles by road east of Lagos and 25 miles north of the Benin river. It has a population of 1,147,188 as at 2006 census and a projected population for 2021 of 1,782,000. The indigenous ethnic group is Benin and their language is Benin. The major businesses of the inhabitants include transportation and petty trading. However, there are two brewing factories, a petroleum storage depot, a battery assembling factory, and four small scale pharmaceutical production factories etc. Benin City is home to some of Nigeria's institutions of higher learning namely; the University of Benin, Tayo Akpata University of Education, Benson Idahosa University, and Wellspring University. Benin City consists of four (4) local government areas (LGAs) out of the eighteen LGAs in Edo State. The four LGAs are Egor, Oredo, Ikpoba-Okha, and Uhumwunode LGAs.⁴¹

University of Benin (UNIBEN) is a federal tertiary education institution that was founded in 1970. It started as an institute of technology and was accorded the status of a full-fledged university by National University Commission (NUC) on the 1st of June, 1971. The university is officially accredited and recognized by the NUC, Nigeria. The university offers courses at various levels; diploma, undergraduate and postgraduate.⁴² The university has two campuses – Ugbowo and Ekehuan campuses both of which are located in Benin City. Ugbowo campus is the main campus and is located in Egor LGA. While Ekehuan campus is located at Oredo LGA.⁴¹ The current vice chancellor is Prof. Lilian I. Salami. It has an undergraduate student enrollment range of 40,000 – 44,999 students made up of both full-time and part-time students; and 4,000 – 4,499 academic staff. The faculties in UNIBEN include Agriculture, Arts, Education, Engineering, Environmental Sciences, Law, Life Sciences, Management Sciences, Pharmacy, Physical Sciences, and Social Science. There is also a college of medical sciences which include School of Medicine, Dentistry, and Basic Medical Sciences.⁴²

Each faculty is made up of a number of degree programs except the faculties of Law, Pharmacy, Dentistry and Medicine which has one-degree program. Some degree programs require four years for their completion, others five years and at most six years. For the purpose of this research, every faculty in UNIBEN was proportionally represented by a chosen degree program.

The University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH) is a tertiary health facility that is in close proximity to UNIBEN. Human papillomavirus vaccine was intermittently available at UBTH at a cost of ₦15,000 to ₦20,000 per dose as at the time of this study.

3.2 STUDY DESIGN

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used for this study.

3.3 STUDY DURATION

This study was carried out between 2021 to 2023.

3.4 STUDY POPULATION

The study population comprised of full-time mid-level female undergraduates in the University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State.

For a four-year degree program, those in 200 and 300 levels were considered mid-level students. While 300 level students only were taken as mid-level students for a five-year degree program. Those in 300 and 400 levels were regarded as mid-level students for a six-year degree program.

3.5 SELECTION CRITERIA

3.5.1 Inclusion Criteria

Mid-level female undergraduates of the UNIBEN that gave consent.

3.5.2 Exclusion Criteria

Part-time undergraduates of UNIBEN.

Full-time female undergraduates of UNIBEN who were not available at the time of the study.

3.6 SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

The minimum sample size (n) was calculated using the Cochran formula for a cross-sectional study.⁴³

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Where:

n = minimum sample size

Z = standard normal deviation set at 1.96 (at 95% confidence interval)

d = degree of precision set at 0.05

p = prevalence rate of a particular characteristics of the target population (a prevalence rate of 31.2% was used. This was the proportion of respondents that had a correct knowledge of HPV vaccine based on a study that was carried out among undergraduate medical students of UNIBEN. The study was published in the Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Healthcare, 2016.)²²

$$p = 0.312$$

$$q = 1 - p$$

$$= 1 - 0.312$$

$$= 0.688$$

Hence:

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.312 \times 0.688}{0.05^2}$$

$$= 329$$

To make for room non-response, 10% was added to the minimum sample size, utilizing the formula for non-response rate.

$$nf = \frac{n}{1-nr}$$

$$n = \text{minimum sample size} = 329$$

$$nr = \text{non-response rate} = 10\% = 0.10$$

$$nf = \text{final minimum sample size}$$

$$nf = \frac{329}{1-0.10}$$

$$= \frac{329}{0.90}$$

$$= 365$$

Thus, final minimum sample size for this study is 365. However, for this study, a sample size of 400 was used.

3.7 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The respondents were selected using convenience sampling technique.

STAGE 1: COMPUTATION OF NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS PER FACULTY/SCHOOL

A list of the total full-time student enrolment by faculty, school, department, sex, level and course of study for 2019/2020 session (which was the most recent list available) was obtained from the board of academic planning. From this list, the total number of female undergraduates and the total number of female mid-level undergraduates across faculties and school were computed as shown in Table 3.1 below.

TABLE 1: LIST OF FACULTIES/SCHOOL AND THE NUMBER OF FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES AND MID-LEVEL FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES

Faculty/School	Number of female undergraduates	Number of mid-level female undergraduates
Education	5133	2415
Arts	4189	2279
Life Sciences	3113	1628
Management Sciences	1772	854
Basic Medical Sciences	1526	357
Social Sciences	1463	721
Physical Sciences	1314	710
Agriculture	1147	236
Engineering	584	125
Law	581	113
Pharmacy	464	167
Medicine	264	150
Environmental Sciences	204	43
Dentistry	47	18
Total	21802	9816

Table 1: A table showing the number of mid-level female undergraduates and total number of female undergraduates across faculties in the university of Benin.

The next step involved solving for the numbers of respondents to be selected across faculties and school. These numbers were gotten by a series of computations and were displayed in table 3.2.

First, the sampling fraction was gotten by dividing the final minimum sample size (nf) by the total number of mid-level female undergraduates across faculties/school (N).

$$\text{sampling fraction} = \frac{nf}{N}$$

$$\text{Sampling fraction} = \frac{400}{9816}$$

$$\text{Sampling fraction} = 0.0407$$

Then the number of respondents for each faculty and school was calculated using the formula;

$$\text{Number of respondents} = \text{sampling fraction} \times \text{number of midlevel female undergraduates per faculty}$$

$$\text{Number of respondents} = 0.0407 \times C$$

TABLE 2: LIST OF FACULTIES/SCHOOL AND THE NUMBER OF SELECTED RESPONDENTS

Faculty/School	Number of mid-level female undergraduates (C)	Number of selected respondents (0.0407 x C)	Actual number of selected respondents
Education	2415	98.4	99
Arts	2279	92.9	93
Life Sciences	1628	66.3	66
Management Sciences	854	34.8	35
Social Sciences	721	29.3	30*
Physical Sciences	710	28.9	30*
Basic Medical Sciences	357	14.5	15
Agriculture	236	9.6	10
Pharmacy	167	6.8	7
Medicine	150	6.1	6
Engineering	125	5.1	5
Law	113	4.6	5
Environmental Sciences	43	1.8	2
Dentistry	18	0.7	1
Total	9816	399.8	404*

*Decimal numbers less than .5 were rounded up to 0 and those greater than or equal to .5 were rounded up to 1. This brought the total sample size to 402. However, the figures in Social and Physical Sciences were wrongly rounded up which resulted to an extra respondent in both faculties. This brought the sample size to a total of 404.

Table 2: This table shows the number of selected respondents per faculty.

STAGE 2: SELECTION OF DEGREE PROGRAMS

From the list obtained from the board of academic planning, using a simple random sampling method by balloting, a degree program was selected per faculty. A total of fourteen undergraduate degree programs were selected as shown in the table 3.3.

TABLE 3: SELECTED DEGREE PROGRAMS

Faculty/School	Selected Degree Program	Number of Selected Respondents
Education	Human Kinetics and Sport Science	99
Arts	History/International Diplomacy	93
Life Sciences	Microbiology	66
Management Sciences	Accounting	35
Social Sciences	Sociology and Anthropology	30
Physical Sciences	Chemistry	30
Basic Medical Sciences	Physiotherapy	15
Agriculture	Animal Science	10
Pharmacy	Pharmacy	7
Medicine	Medicine	6
Engineering	Computer Engineering	5
Law	Law	5
Environmental Sciences	Estate Management	2
Dentistry	Dentistry	1
Total		404

Table 3: this table shows the selected degree program and the number of respondents in each program.

3.8 DATA MANAGEMENT

3.8.1 DATA COLLECTION AND COLLATION

A structured self-administered questionnaire was used for this study. This questionnaire was designed to contain both open ended and closed ended questions. The questions were grouped into four sections as follows:

Section A: Sociodemographic Characteristics

This section was designed to gather information regarding the respondent's sociodemographic characteristics. These characteristics included age, marital status, religion, ethnic group, course of study, class, parent's level of education, parent's occupation, and the respondent's average monthly allowance.

Section B: Knowledge and Practice Regarding HPV Infection

The knowledge and practice regarding HPV infection among female undergraduate in University of Benin was assessed using a total of fifteen (15) questions which included eleven close-ended and four open-ended questions. These were questions regarding awareness of human papillomavirus, mode of transmission, types of diseases caused and safe sex practice.

Section C: Knowledge, Attitude and Uptake Regarding HPV Vaccination

To assess the knowledge, attitude and uptake regarding HPV vaccination, a total of twenty-one (21) questions were asked and this included nine close-ended questions, three open-ended questions and a 3-point Likert scale that had nine questions to specifically assess the attitude domain.

Section D: Reasons for Vaccination Status

For the last section, two multiple response questions were used to determine the reasons for vaccination and non-vaccination among the respondents.

Method of Data Collection

The questionnaire was self-administered because the study participants were sufficiently educated. However, the researchers were within reach to clarify and assist the respondents where necessary. The questionnaires were distributed in places where the privacy of the respondents was guaranteed.

Data Collation

The completed questionnaires were collected and thoroughly checked for any inconsistencies. Data sorting and coding was done. Data was entered and analyzed with IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 software.

3.8.2 DATA PRESENTATION

The results obtained were presented using tables, charts and prose.

3.8.3 DATA ANALYSIS

Socio-demographic Characteristics:

- Age of respondents: this was assessed and grouped into 17 – 19, 20 – 22, 23 – 25 and ≥ 26 .
- Marital status: this was grouped as ‘single’, or ‘married’
- The occupations of parents/guardians of the students were coded as shown below into skill levels 0 to 4 based on ILO-ISC-08 classification.⁴⁴

Skill level 0: Housewives, students, retired and unemployed etc.

Skill level 1: Farmers, traders, gardeners, labourers, cleaners etc.

Skill level 2: Drivers, tailors, police officers, hairdressers, mechanics, electricians etc.

Skill level 3: Technicians, paralegals, shop managers, radiographers etc.

Skill level 4: Doctors, engineers, lecturers, nurses, accountants, teachers etc.

- Average monthly allowance: this was grouped into ‘<10000’, ‘10000 – 30000’, ‘>30000 – 50000’, and ‘>50000 – 70000’.

Knowledge of HPV Infection:

Nine questions were used to assess respondents' knowledge of HPV infection. The answers were coded as "1 = correct response and 0 = incorrect response". Finally, a composite variable from these questions was generated to categorize respondents as having "good/poor knowledge". These scores were converted into percentages and grouped as follows;

- Good knowledge: $\geq 50\%$
- Poor knowledge: $< 50\%$

Practice Regarding HPV Infection:

Seven questions were asked to assess the respondents' attitude and practice regarding HPV infection. Three of these questions were closed ended, while four were open ended. Only the respondents that have had their sexual debut proceeded to complete the seven questions while those who have not stopped at the initial question.

Knowledge of HPV Vaccination:

Nine questions were used to assess respondents' knowledge of HPV vaccination. Correct response was scored 1 and incorrect response was scored 0. The scores were estimated, converted to percentages and grouped as follows:

- Good knowledge: $\geq 50\%$
- Poor knowledge: $< 50\%$

Attitude Towards HPV Vaccination:

A total of 9 questions were used to assess the attitude of the respondents towards HPV vaccination using a 3-point Likert score (agree, undecided, and disagree). The most appropriate response was given a score of two, least appropriate was given a score of 0, in between the two was given a score of 1. A maximum total score of 18 and minimum total score of 0 was achieved. Respondents who scored ≥ 9 ($\geq 50\%$) were considered to have good attitude, while those who scored < 9 ($< 50\%$) were considered to have poor attitude.

- Good attitude: $\geq 50\%$
- Poor attitude: $< 50\%$

Univariate analysis was done to assess the distribution of variables. Bivariate analysis was carried out to determine the association between socio-demographic characteristics and knowledge, attitude and practice regarding HPV infection and vaccination using Fisher's exact test. The level of significance (p-value) for all statistical association was set at < 0.05 .

For the bivariate analysis, course of study was regrouped into biosciences and non-biosciences. Courses that had immunology and virology in their curriculum (microbiology, pharmacy, physiotherapy, medicine and dentistry) were regarded as biosciences while others (human kinetics and sports science, accounting, history/international diplomacy, law, animal science, sociology and anthropology, computer engineering, and estate management) were grouped as non-bioscience.

Also, father and mother's level of education were regrouped. No formal education and primary level of education were taken as Level 1 while secondary and tertiary levels of education were taken as Level 2.

3.9 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical approval was sought and obtained from the University of Benin Teaching Hospital Ethics and Research Committee. Verbal informed consent was obtained from the respondents before administering the questionnaires. Names and addresses were omitted to ensure confidentiality. The respondents were informed that they had the right to withdraw from the interview at any time and that withdrawal poses no loss or harm.

3.10 STUDY LIMITATION

This study relied on information provided by the respondents and may therefore be limited by recall bias. The sensitivity of the questions also posed a potential for social desirability bias. It may also have been limited by some errors made by the researchers during the course of the study.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

A total of 404 (100% response rate) respondents participated in the survey.

The results are presented as follows:

- Section A: Socio-demographic characteristics
- Section B: Knowledge of HPV infection
- Section C: Determinants of knowledge of HPV infection
- Section D: Attitude and practice regarding HPV infection
- Section E: Knowledge of HPV vaccination
- Section F: Determinants of knowledge of HPV vaccination
- Section G: Attitude towards HPV vaccination
- Section H: Determinants of attitude towards HPV vaccination
- Section I: HPV vaccination status
- Section J: Reasons for HPV vaccination status
- Section K: Factors associated with HPV vaccination status

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

TABLE 4a: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Variables	Frequency (n = 404)	Percent
Age (years)		
17 – 19	68	16.8
20 – 22	246	60.9
23 – 25	80	19.8
≥ 26	10	2.5
Mean age ± SD (21.00 ± 1.978)		
Marital status		
Single	401	99.3
Married	3	0.7
Religion		
Christian	401	99.3
Muslim	2	0.5
Eckist	1	0.2
Ethnic group		
Benin	107	26.5
Igbo	95	23.5
Esan	51	12.6
Urhobo	42	10.4
Yoruba	38	9.4
Ika	26	6.4
Ijaw	22	5.5
Afemai	12	3.0
Others*	11	2.7

*Itsekiri, Kalabari, Ighala, Ibibio, Kwale, Isoko, Igbanke, Idoma, and Tiv.

This table shows the age, marital status, religion and tribe of the respondents. The mean age of the respondents was 21.00 ± 1.978 SD, with 246 (60.9%) of the respondents falling within the 20 – 22 age group. Respondents aged ≥26 years were the least represented group, with only 10 (2.5%) respondents falling within this age bracket.

Only 3 (0.7%) respondents were married. The remaining 401 (99.3%) were single. An overwhelming number of the respondents 401 (99.3%) were Christians, 2 (0.5%) were Muslims and 1 (0.2%) was Eckist.

Majority 107 (26.5%) were Benin, closely followed by Igbo 95 (23.5%). The least represented main ethnic group was Afemai with only 12 (3.0%) respondents. Participants belonging to other tribes such as Itsekiri, Ibibio, Isoko, Ighala, Kwale etc., totaled 11 (2.7%) of the respondents.

TABLE 4b: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Variables	Frequency (n = 404)	Percent
Course of study		
Human kinetics and Sport Science	99	24.5
History/International Studies and Diplomacy	93	23.0
Microbiology	66	16.3
Accounting	35	8.4
Chemistry	30	7.4
Sociology and Anthropology	30	7.4
Physiotherapy	15	3.7
Animal Science	10	2.5
Pharmacy	7	1.7
Medicine	6	1.5
Computer Science	5	1.2
Law	5	1.2
Estate Management	2	0.5
Dentistry	1	0.2
Class		
200	69	17.1
300	324	80.2
400	11	2.7
Father's level of education		
No formal education	4	1.0
Primary	28	6.9
Secondary	102	25.2
Tertiary	270	66.8
Skill level of father		
Skill level 0	35	8.7
Skill level 1	28	6.9
Skill level 2	156	38.6
Skill level 3	18	4.5
Skill level 4	167	41.3

This table shows that 99 (24.5%) respondents were studying Human Kinetics and Sport Science.

This was marginally above History/International Studies and Diplomacy 93 (23.0%). Dentistry 1

(0.2%) had the lowest representation. Majority of the respondents 324 (80.2%) were in 300 level. 400 level had just 11 (2.7%) respondents.

Two hundred and seventy (66.8%) respondents' father had tertiary level of education. Only 4 (1.0%) had no formal education, while 28 (6.9%) had primary level of education. Most of the respondents' fathers had skill level four or two: 167 (41.3%) and 156 (38.6%) respectively. The lowest representation was skill level 3 with 18 (4.5%). Skill level 0 had 35 (8.7%).

TABLE 4c: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Variables	Frequency (n = 404)	Percent
Mother's level of education		
No formal education	5	1.2
Primary	25	6.2
Secondary	133	32.9
Tertiary	241	59.7
Skill level of mother		
Skill level 0	12	3.0
Skill level 1	10	2.5
Skill level 2	255	63.3
Skill level 3	1	0.2
Skill level 4	126	31.0
Monthly allowance of respondents (₦)		
<10,000	74	18.4
10,000 – 30,000	283	70.0
>30,000 – 50,000	45	11.1
>50,000 – 70,000	2	0.5

This table shows the level of education and skill level of respondent's mothers. It also shows the monthly allowance of respondents.

There was continuous increase in the respondents' mothers' level of education from 5 (1.2%) having no formal education to 25 (6.2%) with primary level education, 133 (32.9%) with secondary level of education and finally, 241 (59.7%) with tertiary level of education.

Majority of the respondents' mothers 255 (63.1%) had skill level 2 occupation. Only 1 (0.2%) had skill level 3. And 126 (31.0%) had skill level 4 occupations.

Most of the respondents 283 (70%) had monthly allowance within the range of ₦10,000 – ₦30,000. Only 2 (0.5%) respondents had a monthly allowance within the range of >₦50,000 – ₦70,000. Seventy-four (18.3%) respondents had monthly allowance below ₦10,000.

SECTION B: KNOWLEDGE OF HPV INFECTION

TABLE 5a: RESPONDENTS KNOWLEDGE OF HPV INFECTION

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Heard of HPV (n = 404)		
Yes	225	55.7
No	179	44.3
Source of information (n = 225) *		
Social media/internet	118	52.4
School lectures	67	29.8
Television/radio	59	26.2
Healthcare workers	33	14.7
Friends	20	8.9
Family members	15	6.7
Religious organizations	4	1.7
What type of infection is HPV (n = 225) * *		
Viral	161	71.5
Bacterial	10	4.4
Fungal	8	3.6
Protozoan	6	2.7
I don't know	40	17.8
What is the mode of transmission of HPV (n = 225)		
Sexual intercourse	153	68.0
Faecal-oral	29	12.9
Inhalation	10	4.4
I don't know	33	14.7

*Multiple response question

**Frequency (n) was 225 because these were the respondents that have heard of HPV and went on to answer subsequent questions in this section.

More than half (55.7%) of the respondents have heard of HPV. While one hundred and seventy-nine (44.3%) have not heard. For those that have heard, the most common source of information was social media/internet 118 (52.4%). School lectures and television/radio followed with 67 (29.8%) and 59 (26.2%) respectively. Religious organization was the least with 4 (1.7%).

One hundred and sixty-one (71.9%) of the respondents that have heard about HPV correctly identified HPV as a viral infection. Bacterial, 10 (4.4%), was the most common wrong answer. Forty (17.8%) respondents didn't know what type of infection HPV is.

Majority of the respondents 153 (68.0%) that have heard about HPV correctly chose sexual intercourse as mode of transmission of HPV. Twenty-nine (12.9%) and 10 (4.4%) respondents wrongly chose faecal-oral and inhalation as modes of transmission of HPV respectively.

TABLE 5b: RESPONDENTS KNOWLEDGE OF HPV INFECTION

Variables (n = 225)	Frequency	Percent
HPV causes? *		
Cervical cancer	72	32.0
Genital warts	66	29.3
HIV	12	5.3
Penile cancer	6	2.7
Oral cancer	5	2.2
I don't know	64	28.4
HPV infects?		
Both males and females	166	73.8
Females only	56	24.9
Males only	3	1.3
Risk factors for HPV infection are? *		
Multiple sexual partners	123	54.7
Early age at first sexual intercourse	19	8.4
Smoking	9	4.0
Obesity	1	0.4
I don't know	73	32.4
Can one transmit HPV to their partners even without signs and symptoms?		
Yes	126	56.0
No	14	6.2
I don't know	85	37.8

*Multiple response questions

This table shows that close to one-third (32.0%) of respondents who were aware of HPV correctly identified it as the cause of cervical cancer. Also, 66 (28.4%), 6 (2.7%) and 5 (2.2%) respondents correctly identified HPV as the cause of genital warts and possible cause of penile and oral cancers respectively.

Majority of the respondents who were aware of HPV 166 (73.8%) knew that HPV can infect both males and female, which is correct. While 56 (24.9%) and 3 (1.3%) chose only females and only males respectively.

More than half of the respondents 123 (54.7%) identified multiple sexual partners as a risk factor for HPV infection. Nineteen (8.4%) picked early age at first sexual intercourse. Both are known risk factors for HPV infection. Only 1 (0.4%) respondent wrongly chose obesity. And 73 (32.4%) didn't know any risk factor for HPV infection.

More than half of the respondents 126 (56.0%) knew that an infected person without symptoms/signs can transmit HPV to others. Fourteen (6.2%) wrongly answered no. While 85 (37.8%) answered they don't know.

Figure 1: A pie chart showing the respondents knowledge of HPV infection

SECTION C: DETERMINANTS OF KNOWLEDGE OF HPV INFECTION

TABLE 6: DETERMINANTS OF RESPONDENTS KNOWLEDGE OF HPV INFECTION

Determinants	Knowledge of HPV infection		p-value
	Good Freq (%)	Poor Freq (%)	
Age of respondents (years)			
17 – 19	15 (22.1)	53 (77.9)	0.007
20 – 22	99 (40.2)	147 (59.8)	
23 – 25	37 (46.3)	43 (53.8)	
≥26	6 (60.0)	4 (40.0)	
Class (level)			
200	10 (14.5)	59 (85.5)	<0.001
300	136 (42.0)	188 (58.0)	
400	11 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	
Course of study			
Non-biosciences	85 (27.5)	224 (72.5)	<0.001
Biosciences	72 (75.8)	23 (24.2)	
Father's level of education			
Level 1	8 (25.0)	24 (75.0)	0.129
Level 2	149 (40.0)	223 (60.0)	
Mother's level of education			
Level 1	10 (33.3)	20 (67.7)	0.565
Level 2	147 (39.3)	227 (60.7)	
Respondents' monthly allowance (₦)			
<10,000	27 (36.5)	47 (63.5)	0.844
10,000 – 30,000	109 (38.5)	174 (61.5)	
>30,000 – 50,000	20 (44.4)	25 (55.6)	
>50,000 – 70,000	1 (50.0)	1 (50.0)	

This table shows that the knowledge of HPV infection got better with increasing age. Fifteen (22.1%) respondents within age group 17 – 19 years had a good knowledge of HPV infection. This increased to 99 (40.2%) respondents in age group 20 – 22 years. Then, 6 (60%) in ≥26 years

respondents. Poor knowledge decreased with increasing age respectively. This was statistically significant (p-value = 0.007)

All the respondents 11 (100.0%) in 400 level had good knowledge of HPV infection. Respondents in 200 level had the poorest knowledge 59 (85.5%). Respondents in 300 level was intermediate with 136 (42.0%) and 188 (58.0%) having good and poor knowledge respectively. This association was statistically significant (p-value = <0.001)

Majority of the respondents 75 (75.8%) in biosciences had good knowledge of HPV infection which was the opposite of what was obtained among respondents in non-bioscience courses where 224 (72.5%) had poor knowledge of HPV infection. This association was statistically significant (p-value = <0.001)

More than one-third of respondents 149 (40%) whose fathers had level 2 education (secondary and tertiary level of education) had good knowledge of HPV infection. While majority of the respondents 24 (75.0%) whose father had level 1 education (no formal education and primary level of education) had poor knowledge of infection. However, this was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.129)

More than one-third of respondents 147 (39.3%) whose mothers had level 2 education (secondary and tertiary level of education) had good knowledge of HPV infection. While majority of the respondents 20 (67.7%) whose mothers had level 1 education (no formal education and primary level of education) had poor knowledge of infection. This association was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.567)

There was a continuous increase in the percentages of respondents who had good knowledge of HPV infection (and reciprocal decrease in percentages of those who had poor knowledge) as their monthly allowances increase (36.5%, 38.5%, 44.4% and 50% for respondents with <₦10,000, ₦10,000 – ₦30,000, >₦30,000 – ₦50,000 and >₦50,000 – ₦70,000 allowances respectively). This was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.844)

SECTION D: PRACTICE REGARDING HPV INFECTION

TABLE 7a: RESPONDENTS PRACTICE REGARDING HPV INFECTION

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Have you had vaginal intercourse in the past four weeks? (n = 404)		
No	338	83.7
Yes	66	16.3
How old were you at your first sexual intercourse? (n =404) (years)		
Never had sex	128	31.7
<14	49	12.1
14 – 17	88	21.8
18 – 21	120	29.7
>21	19	4.7
Mean ± SD = 16.87 ± 3.6		
How many sexual partners (with or without) have you had since your first sexual intercourse (n = 276) *		
1 – 2	137	49.6
3 – 5	110	39.8
6 – 10	27	9.7
>10	2	0.7

*Frequency (n) is 276 because this was the number of respondents that have had sex and went on to answer subsequent questions in this section.

This table shows that majority of the respondents 338 (83.7%) had not had sex in the past four weeks prior to the survey, while 66 (16.3%) have had sex within the same time frame.

One hundred and twenty-eight (31.7%) respondents have never had sex. While 276 (68.3%) respondents have had sex. For those that have had sex, the mean age of first sexual intercourse was 16.87 ± 3.6 years. And majority 120 (29.7%) had first sexual intercourse between age 18 – 21 years. Forty-nine (12.1%) respondents had first sexual intercourse below the age of 14 years. Only 19 (4.7%) respondents had first sexual intercourse at above 21 years.

Also, for the respondents that have had sex, majority 137 (49.6%) have had between 1 – 2 sexual partners. Twenty-seven (9.7%) respondents have had between 6 – 10 sexual partners. Only 2 (0.7%) respondents have had more than 10 sexual partners.

TABLE 7b: RESPONDENTS PRACTICE REGARDING HPV INFECTION

Variables	Frequency (n = 276)	Percent
Have you ever used a condom?		
Yes	182	65.9
No	94	34.1
Did you used a condom the past time you had sex?		
No	163	59.1
Yes	113	40.9
How many times have you had sex in the last six months?		
1 – 2 times	49	17.8
3 – 5 times	63	22.7
6 – 10 times	46	16.7
>10 times	33	12.0
None	85	30.8
How many times did you used a condom while having sex in the past six months?		
1 – 2 times	59	21.4
3 – 5 times	46	16.7
6 – 10 times	38	13.7
> 10 times	1	0.4
None	132	47.8

Close to two-thirds of the respondents that have had sex 182 (65.9%) have used condom. While 94 (34.1%) respondents have not.

More than half of the respondents that have had sex 163 (59.1%) did not use condom the last time they had sexual intercourse. While 113 (40.9%) used condom the last time they had sex.

Most of the respondents that have had sex 85 (30.8%) have not had sex in the past six months. While 63 (22.7%) respondents have had sex about 3-5 times in the past six months. And 33 (12.0%) respondents have had sex more than 10 times within the same time frame. Nearly half of the respondents that have had sex 132 (47.8%) did not use a condom during sexual intercourse in

the past six months. Fifty-nine (21.4%) had used a condom 1 – 2 times, while only 1 (0.4) respondent have used condom more than 10 times within the same time frame.

SECTION E: KNOWLEDGE OF HPV VACCINATION

TABLE 8a: RESPONDENTS KNOWLEDGE OF HPV VACCINATION

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Have you heard of HPV vaccine? (n = 404)	277	66.8
No	127	31.4
Yes		
Source of information? (n = 127)* §		
Social media/internet	62	48.8
Television/radio	33	26.4
Healthcare workers	30	23.6
Family/friends	28	22.0
Class lectures	10	7.9
Religious organization	3	0.2
What diseases can be prevented using HPV vaccine (n = 127)[§]		
Cervical cancer	85	66.9
Genital warts	56	44.1
Genital herpes	22	17.3
I don't know	22	17.3
Which gender should be vaccinated (n = 127)		
Both males and females	74	58.3
Females only	43	33.9
Males only	2	1.6
I don't know	8	6.3

*Frequency (n) was 127 because this was the number of respondents that have heard of HPV vaccine and were qualified to answer subsequent questions in this section.

§Multiple response question

Almost two-thirds (66.8%) of the respondents have not heard of HPV vaccine.

For the respondents 127 (31.4%) that have heard of HPV vaccine, majority indicated social media/internet as their source of information (48.8%). The second commonest source of information was television/radio (26.4%), while religious organization is the least source of information (0.2%).

The larger proportion (66.9%) of the respondents that have heard of HPV vaccine said it can be used to prevent cervical cancer. About 56 (44.1%) and 22 (17.3%) said it can be used to prevent genital warts and genital herpes respectively. While 22 respondents (17.3%) indicated they don't know what diseases can be prevented with HPV vaccine.

More than half of the respondents 73 (58.3%) that have heard of HPV vaccine said both male and females should be vaccinated. Close to one-third said only females should get the vaccine, while two respondents said only males. Eight respondents answered 'I don't know'.

TABLE 8b: RESPONDENTS KNOWLEDGE OF HPV VACCINATION

Variables (n = 127)	Frequency	Percent
When is the ideal period to commence HPV vaccination?		
Before first sexual intercourse	72	56.7
After first sexual intercourse	8	6.3
I don't know	47	37.0
Is the vaccine available in Nigeria?		
Yes	68	53.5
No	5	3.9
I don't know	54	37.0
Do you know where to obtain the vaccine in your environment?		
No	94	74.0
Yes	33	26.0
How many doses of the vaccine is enough to confer immunity against the disease?		
One	2	1.6
Two	21	16.5
I don't know`	104	81.9
How much does it cost to get vaccinated (₦)?		
<15,000	5	3.9
15,000 – 30,000	6	4.7
>30,000	2	1.6
Free	5	3.9
I don't know	109	85.9

More than half of the respondents that were aware of HPV vaccination 72 (56.7%) agreed that the ideal period to commence the vaccination is before first sexual intercourse. Few respondents 8 (6.3%) were of the opinion that the ideal period is after first sexual intercourse. Forty-seven (37%) said they don't know the ideal period for HPV vaccination.

More than half of the respondents that were aware of HPV vaccination 68 (53.5%) said the vaccine is available in Nigeria. Five respondents (3.9%) said the vaccine is not available in Nigeria. While

close to half of the respondents (42.5%) said they don't know if the vaccine is available in Nigeria or not.

Only 36 (26.0%) of the respondents that know about HPV vaccination knew where to obtain the vaccine in their environment, while majority (74.0%) didn't know.

Almost nine-tenths (81.9%) of the respondents did not know the number of doses of the vaccine required to confer immunity against the virus. Twenty-one (16.5%) said two doses, while only 2 respondents (1.6%) said one dose.

Majority of the respondents 109 (85.9%) that had heard of HPV vaccine said that they did not know the cost of the vaccine. Few respondents 5 (3.9%) were of the opinion that the vaccine is free. While 6 respondents (4.7%) gave a cost of ₦15,000 - ₦30,000 and 5 respondents gave a cost below ₦15,000.

Figure 2: A pie chart showing the respondents knowledge of HPV vaccination

SECTION F: DETERMINANTS OF KNOWLEDGE OF HPV INFECTION

TABLE 9: DETERMINANTS OF RESPONDENTS KNOWLEDGE OF HPV VACCINATION

Determinants	Knowledge of HPV vaccine		p-value
	Good Freq (%)	Poor Freq (%)	
Age of respondents (years)			
17-19	12 (17.6)	56 (82.4)	<0.001
20-22	65 (26.4)	181 (73.6)	
23-25	23 (28.8)	57 (71.3)	
≥26	3 (30.0)	7 (70.0)	
Course of study			
Non-bioscience	56 (18.1)	253 (81.9)	<0.001
Bioscience	47 (49.5)	48 (50.5)	
Class (level)			
200	9 (13.0)	60 (87.0)	<0.001
300	85 (26.2)	239 (73.8)	
400	9 (81.8)	2 (18.2)	
Father's LOE			
Level 1	5 (15.6%)	27 (84.4%)	0.211
Level 2	98 (26.3%)	274 (73.7%)	
Mother's LOE			
Level 1	7 (23.3)	23 (76.7)	1.000
Level 2	96 (25.7)	278 (74.3)	
Respondents monthly allowance (₦)			
<10,000	17 (23.0)	57 (77.0)	0.302
10,000 – 30,000	70 (24.7)	213 (75.3)	
>30,000 – 50,000	16 (35.6)	29 (64.4)	
>50,000 – 70,000	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)	

This table shows that the highest proportion of respondents that had good knowledge of HPV vaccine were ≥26 years old (30%). Majority of the respondents 56 (82.4%) in the age bracket of 17

– 19 years had poor knowledge of HPV vaccine. There was a trend that shows that the higher the age of the respondents, the better the knowledge of HPV vaccine, vice versa. This was however not statistically significant (p-value = 0.419).

Almost half 47 (49.5%) of the respondents who were studying bioscience courses had good knowledge of HPV vaccination. Majority of the respondents 253 (81.9%) of the respondents who were studying non-bioscience courses had poor knowledge of HPV vaccination. This association was statistically significant (p-value = <0.001).

Most of the respondents 9 (81.8%) who were in 400 level had good knowledge of HPV vaccination. Whereas most of the respondents 60 (87.0%) who were in 200 level had poor knowledge. There was a trend that shows that knowledge of HPV vaccine increased with increase in class level of respondents. This association was statistically significant (p = <0.001).

Few respondents 5 (15.6%) whose father had level 1 education (no formal education and primary level of education) had good knowledge of HPV vaccination. Overwhelming majority 27 (84.4%) had poor knowledge. Whereas only 98 (26.3%) respondents whose father had level 2 education (secondary and tertiary level of education) had good knowledge of HPV vaccination. This association was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.211)

Only 7 (23.3%) respondents whose mothers had level 1 education (no formal education and primary level of education) had good knowledge of HPV vaccination. Majority 23 (76.7%) had poor knowledge. Meanwhile only 96 (25.7%) respondents whose mothers had level 2 education (secondary and tertiary level of education) had good knowledge of HPV vaccination. This association was not statistically significant (p-value = 1.000).

Only 35.6% of respondents who received between more than ₦50,000 to 70,000 monthly allowance had good knowledge of HPV vaccination. Whereas, the two respondents that gets above ₦70,000 per month had poor knowledge. However, this was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.302)

SECTION G: ATTITUDE TOWARDS HPV VACCINATION

TABLE 10: RESPONDENTS ATTITUDE TOWARDS HPV VACCINATION

Variables	Disagree (n = 404) Freq (%)	Undecided (n =404) Freq (%)	Agree (n=404) Freq (%)
HPV vaccine is effective in preventing cervical cancer	14 (3.5)	236 (58.4)	154 (38.1)
I will take the vaccine if I feel at risk of getting HPV infection	59 (16.6)	217 (53.7)	128 (31.7)
I feel it is better to be vaccinated before becoming sexually active	17 (4.2)	172 (42.6)	215 (53.2)
The cost of the vaccine discourages me from getting vaccinated	59 (14.6)	293 (72.5)	52 (12.9)
I will use the vaccine if it is available in the health center to students at subsidized price	26 (6.4)	180 (44.6)	198 (49.0)
I feel only sexually active ladies should get the vaccine	176 (43.6)	180 (44.6)	48 (11.9)
HPV vaccine may have long term negative effects	50 (12.4)	311 (77.0)	43 (10.6)
More information on HPV and its vaccine would be needed before I take the vaccine	19 (4.7)	112 (27.7)	273 (67.7)
The vaccine should be included in the National Program for Immunization schedule	7 (1.7)	137 (33.9)	260 (64.4)

More than one-thirds 154 (38.1%) of the respondents agreed that HPV vaccine is effective in preventing cervical cancer. More than half 236 (58.4%) were undecided. Majority 215 (53.2%) also agreed that it is better to take the vaccine before becoming sexually active

Higher proportion of the respondents 273 (67.7%) said that they would need more information on HPV and its vaccine before they would take the vaccine.

Majority of the respondents 260 (64.4%) were of the opinion that HPV vaccination should be included in the National Program for Immunization schedule.

More than two-thirds of the respondents 311 (77.0%) could not tell whether HPV vaccine may have long term negative effects or not. Also, most of the respondents 293 (72.5%) were undecided about the cost of vaccine being a discouragement for its uptake.

TABLE 11: SCORING OF RESPONDENTS ATTITUDE TOWARDS HPV VACCINATION

Variables	Appropriate (n = 404) Freq (%)	Inappropriate (n = 404) Freq (%)
HPV vaccine is effective in preventing cervical cancer	154 (38.1)	250 (61.9)
I will take the vaccine if I feel at risk of getting HPV infection	59 (14.6)	345 (85.4)
I feel it is better to be vaccinated before becoming sexually active	215 (53.2)	189 (46.8)
The cost of the vaccine discourages me from getting vaccinated	59 (14.6)	345 (85.4)
I will use the vaccine if it is available in the health center to students at subsidized price	198 (49.0)	206 (51.0)
I feel only sexually active ladies should get the vaccine	48 (11.9)	356 (88.)
HPV vaccine may have long term negative effects	50 (12.4)	354 (87.6)
More information on HPV and its vaccine would be needed before I take the vaccine	385 (95.3)	19 (4.7)
The vaccination should be included in the National Program for Immunization schedule	260 (64.4)	144 (35.6)

Most of the respondents 250 (61.9%) gave an inappropriate response to the statement “HPV vaccine is effective in preventing cervical cancer”. More than two-thirds 345 (85.4%) of the responses to “I will take the vaccine if I feel at risk of getting HPV infection” were inappropriate. The proportions of respondents that had appropriate and inappropriate responses to the statement ‘I feel it is better to be vaccinated before becoming sexually active were close: 215 (53.2%) and 189 (46.8%) respectively. Majority of the respondents 385 (95.3%) responded appropriately to “more information on HPV and its vaccine would be needed before I take the vaccine”. And 354 (87.6%) responded inappropriately to “HPV vaccine may have long term negative effects”.

Figure 3: A pie chart showing respondents attitude towards HPV vaccination

SECTION H: DETERMINANTS OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS HPV VACCINATION

TABLE 12: DETERMINANTS OF RESPONDENTS ATTITUDE TOWARDS HPV VACCINATION

Determinants	Overall attitude		p-value
	Positive Freq (%)	Negative Freq (%)	
Age of respondents (years)			
17 – 19	15 (22.1)	53 (77.9)	0.016
20 – 22	81 (32.9)	165 (67.1)	
23 – 25	37 (46.3)	43 (53.7)	
≥26	4 (40.0)	6 (60.0)	
Course of study			
Non-bioscience	83 (26.9)	226 (73.1)	<0.001
Bioscience	54 (56.8)	41 (43.2)	
Class			
200	20 (29.0)	49 (71.0)	0.003
300	108 (33.3)	216 (66.7)	
400	9 (81.8)	2 (18.2)	
Father's LOE			
Level 1	9 (28.1)	23 (71.9)	0.562
Level 2	128 (34.4)	244 (65.6)	
Mother's LOE			
Level 1	12 (40.0)	18 (60.0)	0.548
Level 2	125 (33.4)	249 (66.6)	
Respondents monthly allowance (₦)			
<10,000	27 (36.5)	47 (63.5)	0.077
10,000 – 30,000	88 (31.1)	195 (68.9)	
>30,000 – 50,000	22 (48.9)	23 (51.1)	
>50,000 – 70,000	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)	

This tables shows that respondents within 17 – 19 years age bracket had the least proportion 15 (22.1%) of respondents with good attitude towards HPV vaccination while those within the 23 – 25

years age bracket, had the highest proportion 37 (46.3%) of those with good attitude towards HPV vaccination. Generally, younger respondents had higher proportion of respondents with negative attitude while older respondents had higher proportions of those with good attitude towards HPV vaccination. This association was statistically significant (p-value = 0.016).

Respondents in biosciences had a higher proportion 54 (56.8%) of those with good attitude towards HPV vaccination when compared to respondents from non-biosciences 83 (26.9%). This association was statistically significant (p-value = <0.001).

With increase in class, there was a progressive increase the proportion of respondents with positive attitude towards HPV vaccination. The higher the class of the respondents, the better the attitude towards HPV vaccination and vice versa. This association was statistically significant (p-value = 0.003).

Almost half 22 (48.9%) of respondents who received between more than ₦30,000 to ₦50,000 monthly allowance had positive attitude towards HPV vaccination. While more than half of respondents 195 (68.9%) who received between ₦10,000 to ₦30,000 monthly allowance had negative attitude towards HPV vaccination. This association was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.07).

SECTION I: HPV VACCINE UPTAKE (VACCINATION STATUS)

TABLE 13: RESPONDENTS' HPV VACCINE UPTAKE (VACCINATION STATUS)

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Have you received HPV vaccine?		
No	397	98.3
Yes	7	1.7
If yes, how many does have you received (n = 7)*		
One	6	85.7
Two	1	14.3
Where did you receive the vaccine (n = 7)		
Hospital	3	42.8
Church	1	14.3
Community mobile service	1	14.3
Irowa medical center	1	14.3
The market (an out-reach)	1	14.3

*Frequency (n) is 7 because this was the number of respondents that have received at least one dose of HPV vaccine and answered subsequent questions in this section.

This table shows that only 7 (1.7%) respondents had been vaccinated. Out of these 7, only 1 (14.2%) respondent has received two doses, while 6 (85.7%) respondents have received just a single dose. Three hundred and ninety-seven (98.3%) respondents have not received the vaccine.

Three respondents received the vaccine from hospital. One respondent received the vaccine from a medical center. One respondent each received the vaccine from church, community mobile service and the market respectively.

Figure 4: A pie chart showing the number and percentages of respondent that have taken at least one dose of HPV vaccine.

SECTION J: REASONS FOR HPV VACCINATION STATUS

TABLE 14: REASONS FOR VACCINATION AND NON-VACCINATION

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Reasons for taking the vaccine*		
Parents' recommendation	4	57.1
Health workers' recommendation	4	57.1
Friends' recommendation	1	14.3
Personal decision	1	14.3
Reasons for not being vaccinated*		
Lack of awareness	236	58.4
Never considered it	102	25.2
Don't know where to obtain the vaccine	52	12.9
The vaccine is not affordable	43	10.6
Don't know or uncertain about the vaccine's usefulness	37	9.2
Fear of side effects	29	7.2
Religious reasons	4	1.0

*Multiple response questions

The main reasons for vaccination were parents' and health workers' recommendations. More than half of the reasons for not being vaccinated was lack of awareness 236 (58.4%). "Never considered it" 102 (25.2%) came a distant second as the reason for not being vaccinated. Fifty-two (12.9%) and forty-three (10.6) respondents indicated that "the vaccine is not affordable" and "don't know where to obtain the vaccine" as the reasons for not being vaccinated respectively. Religious reasons 4 (1.0%) was the least indicated reason for not being vaccinated.

SECTION K: FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH VACCINATION STATUS

TABLE 15: FACTORS ASSOCIATED RESPONDENTS HPV VACCINATION STATUS

Factors	HPV vaccine status		p-value
	Vaccinated Freq (%)	Unvaccinated Freq (%)	
Age of respondents (years)			
17 – 19	1 (1.5)	67 (98.5)	0.276
20 – 22	4 (1.6)	242 (98.4)	
23 – 25	1 (1.3)	79 (98.7)	
≥ 26	1 (10.0)	10 (90.0)	
Course of study			
Non-bioscience	3 (1.0)	306 (99.0)	0.056
Bioscience	4 (4.2)	91 (95.8)	
Class (level)			
200	1 (1.4)	68 (98.6)	0.017
300	4 (1.2)	320 (98.8)	
400	2 (18.2)	9 (81.8)	
Father’s level of education			
Level 1	0 (0.0)	32 (100.0)	1.000
Level 2	7 (1.9)	365 (98.1)	
Mother’s level of education			
Level 1	0 (0.0)	30 (100.0)	1.000
Level 2	7 (1.9)	367 (98.1)	
Respondents monthly allowance (₦)			
<10,000	1 (1.4)	73 (98.6)	0.313
10,000 – 30,000	4 (1.4)	279 (98.6)	
>30,000 – 50,000	2 (2.2)	43 (95.6)	
>50,000 – 70,000	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)	

Most of the vaccinated respondents 4 (1.6%) were within 20 – 22 age brackets. However, the percentages of the unvaccinated respondents were more than 90.0% across all the age groups. This association was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.276).

More than half of the vaccinated respondents 4 (1.2%) were from 300 level. However, majority of the unvaccinated respondents 320 (98.8) were also from 300 level. The association between class and vaccination was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.017).

More than 95 percent of all respondents across all the four ranges of monthly allowance were unvaccinated. The association between income and vaccination status was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.313).

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

Universities are commonly viewed as the custodians of knowledge, and as such, university students are expected to possess higher levels of knowledge in certain areas when compared to the general public and to be more open-minded and willing to adopt new development. When university students display a low level of knowledge, it can only indicate that the level of knowledge among the wider populace is even poorer. This study was done to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice regarding HPV infection and vaccination.

Four hundred and four respondents participated in this study. The mean age of the respondents was 21 ± 1.98 years. Majority of the respondents were Christians, this was not surprising as the predominant religion in southern Nigeria, where the study area is located is Christianity.⁴¹

This study revealed that just above half of the respondents had heard of HPV infection. This could be attributed to the fact that unlike human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) which are pandemics and have been largely publicized nationally and globally, HPV infection has received little attention nationally. This finding is however in contrast to findings from a study conducted among medical and allied health students in Northern Nigeria where majority (80.0%) of the participants had heard of HPV infection.⁴⁵ About one-third were able to correctly identify that HPV is a viral disease and that is sexually transmitted and few identified it as a cause cervical cancer. This is similar to findings in a study conducted among undergraduate students of AAU were only 45.0% and 44.1% of the respondents of HPV infection knew that HPV was a viral infection and is sexually transmitted, respectively. And 35.5% knew that HPV can cause cervical cancer.³⁶ The overall score for knowledge showed that only a little over one-third of the

respondents had good knowledge of HPV infection. This could be because majority of the respondents were studying non-bioscience courses which does not include virology and immunology as part of their curriculum thereby limiting their knowledge about HPV infection. Also, a of lack of detailed information about HPV infection since most of the respondents who were aware of HPV infection got their information from social media. This is similar to results from studies conducted in Osun, Edo and Lagos States, that found that only 23.9%, 14.8% and 3.0% respectively of the respondents had good knowledge of HPV infection.^{13,33,36} Poor knowledge about HPV puts an individual at a higher risk of contracting and transmitting the virus, contributing to the overall burden of infection in the population. Also, poor knowledge may result in low participation in screening programs, reduced vaccine coverage, and limited implementation of preventive strategies.^{8,48}

This study found statistically significant associations between the knowledge of HPV infection, class and course of study. The higher the class of respondents, the better the knowledge of HPV infection. Bioscience courses were found to be associated with better knowledge of HPV infection. The reasons for these findings are not far-fetched because respondents in higher classes are more likely to have been exposed to more information, which in turn would impact their knowledge. Students studying bioscience courses are more likely to have been taught or to have read about HPV in their textbooks compared to students studying non-bioscience courses. This finding is consistent with that of other studies done within Nigeria which showed a statistically significant relationship between class, course of study and knowledge of HPV infection.^{22,45} Non-bioscience courses students make up the bulk of the university undergraduate population. Poor knowledge of HPV infection among these populations may contribute significantly to the proportion of undergraduates who do not follow preventive measures like consistent use of condoms leading to increased risk of contracting HPV infection.¹⁶ Therefore, creating awareness among these groups is paramount in the prevention and control of HPV infection.

The study found that about two-thirds of the respondents have had sex, with the mean age of first sexual intercourse being 16.8 ± 3.6 years, which is slightly lower than findings from the Nigeria Demographic Health Survey (NDHS) done in 2018 where the mean age of first sexual intercourse among girls was found to be 17.2 years.¹² The reason for this difference could be the freedom that comes with living in the university unchecked by parents or guardians. It could also be reflective of the continued trend of an overall decrease in the age of first sexual intercourse among females over the years.¹² Studies have found that earlier age of sexual debut (less than 18 years) is associated with an increased risk of HPV infection and subsequent development of cervical cancer.^{13,36,46} Thus, the finding of the age of first sexual intercourse being below the national average is worrisome and calls for concerted action among different stakeholders to enlighten young girls, especially those newly admitted into the university, on the need and importance of delaying first sexual intercourse till they are armed with experience and awareness on safe sexual practices and ways of preventing HPV infection.

About two-thirds of the respondents that have had sex, used condom during sexual intercourse and almost half had between one to two lifetime sexual partners. These findings are synchronous with other studies conducted among university undergraduates within Nigeria where 52% of participants were found to have had sexual intercourse, 58.6% to have ever used a condom and the median number of sexual partners was two.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ Fewer numbers of lifetime sexual partners have been proven to significantly reduce the risk of contracting STI's including HPV.⁴⁶

This study revealed nearly one-third of the respondents were aware of HPV vaccines which is similar to the results gotten from a study conducted in AAU where only a few (17.0%) of the respondents were aware of HPV vaccines.³⁶ Few of the respondents correctly chose that HPV vaccine is preventive against cervical cancer, that both sexes can take the vaccine, and that the ideal period for vaccination is before sexual debut. These findings are similar although slightly lower than what was obtained from a study conducted among female undergraduates in Lagos where about one-third of the respondents (38.0%) knew that HPV vaccine is preventive against cervical

cancer, one-fifth (23%) knew who should be vaccinated and about one-third (36.2%) knew the ideal period for HPV vaccination.³³ Social media/internet was found to be the commonest source of information among respondents. Television/radio was the second most common source of information. Class lectures came a distant fifth, with only a few of the respondents stating it as their source of information. It would have been expected that class lectures should be among the top commonest source of information on HPV vaccine considering that this study was conducted among undergraduates. This however was not the case. A possible reason could be because majority of the respondents were studying Arts and Social science-related courses where lectures on HPV and its vaccines would likely not be part of the curriculum. This observation is in line with findings from a study done among undergraduate students of Federal University, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, where internet and television/radio were observed to be the two most utilized sources of respondents' information on HPV vaccine.⁵⁰ However, it differs from results observed in a study done in AAU, Ekpoma where healthcare workers (41.0%) were the commonest source of information about HPV vaccine.³⁶ This highlights the need for university administrators to find a way to incorporate sexually transmitted infection (STI) across all courses of study to ensure that majority of the students do not miss out on these important health-promoting lessons. Also, to make detailed and correct information on HPV vaccine available on social media platforms since they have greater appeal among students.

When everything about knowledge of HPV vaccine was put together, this study revealed that majority of the respondents had poor knowledge of HPV vaccine. A possible reason could be the poor knowledge of the infection itself. It stands to reason that poor knowledge of a particular STI will result in poor knowledge of its vaccine. This is in tandem with findings in an undergraduate study conducted in Kano where about two-thirds of the participants were discovered to have an overall poor knowledge of HPV vaccine.⁴¹ University female undergraduates represent an age group where HPV vaccination can have a great impact in preventing future infections and related complications. Poor knowledge of the vaccine can lead to missed opportunities for vaccination.

Also, these female undergraduates may later become mothers and insufficient knowledge of HPV vaccine can hinder their ability to protect their children from HPV infection and related diseases, thus perpetuating the cycle of poor knowledge and poor health outcomes.

Regarding attitude towards HPV vaccination, about three-fifths of the respondents gave inappropriate responses to the statement “HPV vaccine is effective in preventing cervical cancer”. The study also showed that about half of the respondents were aware that it is better to be vaccinated before becoming sexually active. However, this awareness does not translate into willingness to get vaccinated, as the majority of the respondents did not answer affirmatively when asked if they would take the vaccine if they felt at risk of infection. Most of the respondents also gave inappropriate responses to the statement "HPV vaccine may have long-term negative effects". This may be a pointer to misinformation about the vaccine's safety and efficacy resulting in vaccine hesitancy. To further corroborate this, findings showed that nearly all of the respondents responded affirmatively to the statement "more information on HPV and its vaccine would be needed before I take the vaccine". Overall, only one-third of the respondents had a positive attitude towards HPV vaccination. This might be due to a poor knowledge of HPV vaccination and also a reflection of misinformation regarding vaccines stemming from conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic. These findings regarding attitude to HPV vaccination are in contrast to the findings of a study done in Lagos State Polytechnic (LASPOTECH) in 2019 where despite the poor knowledge of HPV and its vaccine among the respondents, most of them (93%) had a positive attitude towards uptake of HPV vaccine.³³ Poor knowledge of HPV vaccination will negatively impact vaccine uptake. This strongly highlights the importance of public education and awareness campaigns on the HPV vaccine and how it works in preventing cervical cancer.

There was an observed progressive increase in knowledge and positive attitude towards HPV vaccination among students across age, academic levels and course which suggests the influence of educational factors on information acquisition and retention. This increased exposure likely contributes to a deeper understanding of HPV vaccination and its benefits. This is similar to a study

done among medical students of the University of Lagos where it was observed that higher proportions of students in 600 level had good knowledge of HPV vaccination.⁵¹

A higher level of knowledge was observed among students studying Bioscience courses and it was statistically significant. This can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, these disciplines have a direct connection to healthcare, and students in these fields receive extensive training in medical sciences, including immunology and infectious diseases. This comprehensive education equips them with a strong foundation in understanding the importance of preventive measures, such as vaccinations, in combating diseases. This is similar to a study done in among female medical and dental students in a tertiary institution in Benin-City, Nigeria that showed significant association between knowledge and attitude towards HPV vaccination and age, faculty, and level of study.²²

The findings of this study revealed that uptake of the HPV vaccine among respondents was very low, as only 1.7% of those surveyed had been vaccinated. This could be due to the poor knowledge of HPV infection and vaccination and negative attitude towards HPV vaccination. Also, unlike other vaccines which are given during childhood as part of the National Programme for Immunization (NPI) schedule, HPV vaccination though part of the NPI schedule is given at a much later period and most parents may not be informed at the end of the earlier routine childhood vaccination that their children would need to be vaccinated at a later time against HPV infection. This finding of low uptake of HPV vaccination is consistent with results of studies done in this same study area but among Medical and Dental students where only 3.7% had taken at least one dose of the vaccination. It is also similar to other previous studies done among undergraduates in other cities in Nigeria such as Lagos (2.6%) and Port Harcourt (5.1%). Low vaccination rates significantly increase the incidence of HPV-related diseases. These diseases impose a substantial economic burden on healthcare systems and societies. The costs associated with diagnosing and treating HPV-related cancers, as well as the long-term effects on quality of life and productivity, can be significant. HPV vaccination not only protects individuals who receive the vaccine but also

contributes to herd immunity. These findings suggest that there is a need for continued efforts to increase awareness of HPV vaccine in Nigeria, particularly among parents and young girls.^{22,27,33}

This study showed that the main factor hindering HPV vaccination uptake was found to be a lack of awareness, with over half of respondents identifying this as the reason. The second most commonly cited explanation for not being vaccinated was that they had never considered vaccination. This is consistent with a study done in Bowen among undergraduates where most (91.0%) gave ignorance of availability of HPV vaccine in Nigeria as some of the reasons for non-vaccination. And about one-fifth (21.0%) did not know where to obtain the vaccine.⁴⁰ But differ from a study done among undergraduate students in Lagos in which the need for more information (33.4%), safety concerns (21.1%) and cost of the vaccine (17.6%) were the three most common reasons for non-vaccination.³³ This finding suggests that, while there has been progress regarding the promotion of the HPV vaccine, more needs to be done to raise awareness and to promote accessibility through measures such as wider availability. On the other hand, the most common reason for receiving HPV vaccine was due to the recommendation of parents and healthcare workers. However, there was a paucity of studies on why vaccinated undergraduate students took the vaccine. This calls for further research to determine specific reasons for vaccination which may help to formulate action plans to enhance HPV vaccine uptake among unvaccinated eligible individuals.

This study also explored the factors associated with HPV vaccination status. The findings showed that there is a relationship between the course of study and vaccine uptake as more than half of those who were vaccinated were studying bioscience courses. A statistical analysis performed to determine the significance revealed that the association between the respondents' course of study and the HPV vaccine uptake was statistically significant. The inclusion of HPV in the curriculum of these health-care related course explains this association.

Respondents who were unaware of HPV vaccination were allowed to answer questions regarding their attitude towards the vaccine, in order to provide insight into their initial perceptions and beliefs.

This study was conducted within a single institution, exclusively involving female participants, and with a majority of them identifying as Christians. Therefore, caution must be exercised when generalizing the findings to a broader population.

CONCLUSION

This study provided valuable insights into the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to HPV infection and vaccination among female undergraduates of UNIBEN.

There was poor knowledge of HPV infection, with older respondents, respondents in higher class, and those studying bioscience courses demonstrating a better knowledge. More than half of the respondents were sexually active and most had just one or two lifetime sexual partners.

Similar to the knowledge of the infection, the knowledge of HPV vaccination was poor and bioscience course, higher class and older age positively affected the knowledge of HPV vaccination. Majority of the respondents had negative attitude towards HPV vaccination which could be due to poor knowledge of the vaccine and the infection.

There was a very low uptake of HPV vaccine, and lack of awareness was the major reason for this. Other notable reasons for the low uptake of the vaccine were 'never considered it', and 'don't know where to obtain it'.

The overall result therefore shows that there is an urgent need for concerted effort among stakeholders (school authorities, government at various level, civil society organizations (CSO) healthcare workers etc.) to create more awareness on human papillomavirus infection and vaccination as well make the vaccine accessible, available and affordable.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

To the Federal Government:

- Introduce HPV vaccination into the routine immunization schedule.
- Allocate adequate funding for the procurement and distribution of HPV vaccines to ensure accessibility and affordability for all eligible individuals.

To State Governments and Civil Society Organizations:

- Collaborate with the federal government to implement and support the national HPV vaccination program, ensuring coverage across all states and regions.
- Integrate HPV education and awareness programs into existing reproductive health initiatives and school health curricula to reach a wider audience, including both students and parents.

- Establish partnerships with local community leaders, religious organizations, and community-based groups to disseminate accurate information about HPV infection, vaccination, and cervical cancer prevention.
- Launch nationwide public awareness campaigns to educate the general population about HPV infection, its link to cervical cancer, and the importance of HPV vaccination as a preventive measure.

To School Authorities:

- Organize regular seminars, workshops, and awareness campaigns within schools to educate students, teachers, and parents about sexually transmitted infections with a focus on HPV infection, HPV vaccination, and preventive measures.
- Collaborate with healthcare providers to facilitate on-campus HPV vaccination programs, ensuring easy access and convenience for students.
- Foster partnerships with local healthcare facilities and organizations to provide accurate information, counseling, and support services related to HPV infection and vaccination.

To Healthcare Workers:

- Actively promote and advocate for HPV vaccination to eligible individuals, including adolescents, young adults, and parents, emphasizing the safety and effectiveness of the vaccine in preventing HPV infection and related diseases.
- Engage in community outreach programs to raise awareness about HPV infection, its consequences, and the availability of HPV vaccines.

REFERENCES

1. Bruni L. The frequency of HPV infection worldwide. *HPV World*. Published online 2020:12-15.
<https://www.hpvworld.com/articles/the-frequency-of-hpv-infection-worldwide/%0A>
2. World Health Organization (WHO). Human papillomavirus (HPV) and cervical cancer Key facts. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland. 2018;20(November 2020):1-7.
3. States M, Strategic WHO, Group A, Grade T, Sage T. Human papillomavirus vaccines: WHO position paper, May 2017. *Epidemiology*. 2017;92(19):241-268.
4. Patel H, Jevé YB, Sherman SM, Moss EL. Knowledge of human papillomavirus and the human papillomavirus vaccine in European adolescents: A systematic review. *Sexually Transmitted Infection*. 2016;92(6):474-479. doi:10.1136/sextrans-2015-052341
5. Mirabello L, Clarke MA, Nelson CW, et al. The intersection of HPV epidemiology, genomics and mechanistic studies of HPV-mediated carcinogenesis. *Viruses*. 2018;10(2). doi:10.3390/v10020080
6. de Martel C, Plummer M, Vignat J, Franceschi S. Worldwide burden of cancer attributable to HPV by site, country and HPV type. *International Journal for Cancer*. 2017;141(4):664-670. doi:10.1002/ijc.30716
7. Chanprasertpinyo W, Rerkswattavorn C. Human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine status and knowledge of students at a university in rural Thailand. *Heliyon*. 2020;6(8):e04625. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04625
8. Dunne EF, Markowitz LE, Saraiya M, et al. CDC grand rounds: Reducing the burden of HPV-associated cancer and disease. *MMWR Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Rep*. 2014;63(4):69-72.
<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24476977%0Ahttp://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/arti>

clerender.fcgi?artid=PMC4584896

9. Bruni L, Saura-Lázaro A, Montoliu A, et al. HPV vaccination introduction worldwide and WHO and UNICEF estimates of national HPV immunization coverage 2010–2019. *Prev Med (Baltim)*. 2021;144. doi:10.1016/j.ypmed.2020.106399
10. Gallagher KE, Lamontagne DS, Watson-jones D. Status of HPV vaccine introduction and barriers to country uptake. *Vaccine*. 2018;36(32):4761-4767. doi:10.1016/j.vaccine.2018.02.003
11. Okunade KS, Sunmonu O, Osanyin GE, Oluwole AA. Knowledge and Acceptability of Human Papillomavirus Vaccination among Women Attending the Gynaecological Outpatient Clinics of a University Teaching Hospital in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2017;2017. doi:10.1155/2017/8586459
12. National Population Commission (NPC)/ICF. Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018. Abuja, Nigeria, and Rockville, Maryland, USA: NPC and ICF; 2019.
13. Nejo YT, Olaleye DO, Odaibo GN. Prevalence and Risk Factors for Genital Human Papillomavirus Infections Among Women in Southwest Nigeria. 2018;6(1):105-112. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29905313><http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/articlerender.fcgi?artid=PMC5997288>
14. Derby A, Mekonnen D, Misgan E, Alemu YM, Woldeamanuel Y, Abebe T. Low level of knowledge about cervical cancer among Ethiopian women: a systematic review and meta-analysis. 2021;16(1):1-9. doi:10.1186/s13027-021-00350-x
15. ICO/IARC HPV Information Centre on HPV and Cancer. *Nigeria: Human Papillomavirus and Related Cancers, Fact Sheet 2021.*; 2021.
16. Anyasi HI, Foss AM. A comparative analysis of cervical cancer prevention between Nigeria and Nordic countries that have experienced a decline in cervical cancer incidence.

International Health. 2021;13(4):307-317. doi:10.1093/inthealth/ihaa062

17. Ilevbare OE, Adegoke AA, Adelowo CM. Drivers of cervical cancer screening uptake in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Heliyon*. 2020;6(3):e03505. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03505
18. Ugwu EO, Obi SN, Ezechukwu PC, Okafor II, Ugwu AO. Acceptability of human papilloma virus vaccine and cervical cancer screening among female health-care workers in Enugu, Southeast Nigeria. *Niger Journal of Clinical Practice*. 2013;16(2):249-252. doi:10.4103/1119-3077.110141
19. Ewelukwa O, Onoka C, Onwujekwe O. Viewing health expenditures, payment and coping mechanisms with an equity lens in Nigeria. *BMC Health Service*. 2013;13(1):87. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-13-87
20. National Bureau of Statistics. 2019 Poverty and Inequality in Nigeria: Executive Summary. *National Bureau of Statistics*. 2020;(May):1-27. www.nigerianstat.gov.ng
21. Makwe CC, Ihuoma R. Human papillomavirus (HPV) infection and vaccines : Knowledge , attitude and perception among female students at the University of Lagos. *Journal of Epidemiology and Global Health*. 2012;2(4):199-206. doi:10.1016/j.jegh.2012.11.001
22. Onowhakpor AO, Omuemu VO, Osagie OL, Odili CG. COMMUNITY MEDICINE AND PRIMARY HEALTH CARE Human Papilloma Virus Vaccination: Knowledge, Attitude and Uptake among Female Medical and Dental Students in a Tertiary Institution. *J Community Med Prim Heal Care*. 2016;28(2):101-108.
23. Bisi-Onyemaechi AI, Chikani UN, Nduagubam O. Reducing incidence of cervical cancer: Knowledge and attitudes of caregivers in Nigerian city to human papilloma virus vaccination. *Infectious Agent*. 2018;13(1):4-9. doi:10.1186/s13027-018-0202-9
24. Husain Y, Alalwan A, Al-Musawi Z, Abdulla G, Hasan K, Jassim G. Knowledge towards human papilloma virus (HPV) infection and attitude towards its vaccine in the kingdom of

- Bahrain: Cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*. 2019;9(9):1-7.
doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2019-031017
25. Akanbi OA, Iyanda A, Osundare F, Opaleye OO. Perceptions of Nigerian Women about Human Papilloma Virus, Cervical Cancer, and HPV Vaccine. *Scientifica (Cairo)*. 2015;2015:1-4. doi:10.1155/2015/285702
 26. Ozyer S, Uzunlar O, Ozler S, et al. Awareness of Turkish female adolescents and young women about HPV and their attitudes towards HPV vaccination. *Asian Pacific J Cancer Prev*. 2013;14(8):4877-4881. doi:10.7314/APJCP.2013.14.8.4877
 27. Ojimah C, Maduka O. Awareness and uptake of human papillomavirus vaccines among female undergraduate students: Implications for cervical cancer prevention in South-South, Nigeria. *Port Harcourt Med J*. 2017;11(3):134-40.
 28. Ndikom CM, Oboh PI. Perception, acceptance and uptake of human papillomavirus vaccine among female adolescents in selected secondary schools in Ibadan, Nigeria. *African J Biomed Res*. 2017;20(3):237-244. doi:10.4314/ajbr.v20i3
 29. Schwendener CL, Kiener LM, Jafflin K, et al. HPV vaccine awareness, knowledge and information sources among youth in Switzerland: A mixed methods study. *BMJ Open*. 2022;12(1):1-11. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2021-054419
 30. Seyma Zehra ALTUNKUREK, Eda SAHIN, Samira Hassan MOHAMED. Knowledge, Attitudes and Behaviors of Somalia Female University Students about Cervical Cancer, Hpv and HPV Vaccine: Cross-Sectional Study. *Relev Epidemiology Hebd*. Published online 2022:1-22.
 31. Khatiwada M, Kartasasmita C, Mediani HS, Delprat C, Van Hal G, Dochez C. Knowledge, Attitude and Acceptability of the Human Papilloma Virus Vaccine and Vaccination Among University Students in Indonesia. *Front Public Health*. 2021;9(June):1-9.

doi:10.3389/fpubh.2021.616456

32. Biyazin T, Yilma A, Yetwale A, Fenta B, Dagnaw Y. Knowledge and attitude about human papillomavirus vaccine among female high school students at Jimma town, Ethiopia. *Human Vaccines*. 2022;18(1):1-9. doi:10.1080/21645515.2022.2036522
33. Esther O. Oluwole, Oluwaseun M. Idowu, Adebola A. Adejimi, Mobolanle R. Balogun GEO. Knowledge, attitude and uptake of human papillomavirus vaccination among female undergraduates in Lagos State, Nigeria. *J Fam Med Prim Care*. 2019;8(11):3628-3633. doi: 10.4103/jfmpe.jfmpe
34. Deng C, Chen X, Liu Y. Human papillomavirus vaccination: coverage rate, knowledge, acceptance, and associated factors in college students in mainland China. *Human Vaccines*. 2021;17(3):828-835. doi:10.1080/21645515.2020.1797368
35. Isabirye A, Asiimwe J, Mbonye M. Factors associated with HPV vaccination uptake in Central Uganda. *East African Journal of Science and Technology*. 2020;1(4):1-16. doi:10.37425/eajsti.v1i4.185
36. Isara AR, Osayi N. Knowledge of Human Papillomavirus and Uptake of its Vaccine among Female Undergraduate Students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria. *J Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*. 2021;33(1):64-75. doi:10.4314/jcmphc.v33i1.6
37. Li SL, Lau YL, Lam TH, Yip PSF, Fan SYS, Ip P. HPV vaccination in Hong Kong: Uptake and reasons for non-vaccination amongst Chinese adolescent girls. *Vaccine*. 2013;31(49):5785-5788. doi:10.1016/j.vaccine.2013.10.027
38. Afolabi EK, Ogunsanwo OO, Oyebamiji SO, Ani OB . Low uptake of human papillomavirus vaccination and cervical cancer screening among female undergraduates of a Nigerian University. *Trop J Obs Gynaecol*. 2019;36(4):373-377. doi:10.4103/TJOG.TJOG
39. LaJoie AS, Kerr JC, Clover RD, Harper DM. Influencers and preference predictors of HPV

- vaccine uptake among US male and female young adult college students. *Papillomavirus Res.* 2018;5(January):114-121. doi:10.1016/j.pvr.2018.03.007
40. Idowu A, Olowookere SA, Israel OK, Akinwumi AF. Human Papillomavirus Vaccine Acceptability and Uptake among Medical and Paramedical Students of a Nigerian Tertiary Health Institution. *Journal of Public Health Vol 7, 2019, Pages 143-150.* 2019;7(4):143-150. doi:10.12691/ajphr-7-4-3
 41. Edo State Government. History of Edo State, Benin City. 2014. Available from <https://www.edostate.gov.ng/about-edo-2/>. [Accessed on 30 November, 2021]
 42. University of Benin. History of University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State. 2020. Available from: <https://www.uniben.edu.ng/about/history/> [Accessed on 30 November, 2021]
 43. Cochran W. Sampling Techniques. 3rd ed. New York: Wiley; 1977. <https://hwbdocuments.env.nm.gov/Los%20Alamos%20National%20Labs/General/14447.pdf> [Accessed on 30 November, 2021]
 44. International Labour Organization (ILO). International Standard Classification of Occupation. 2008; [Accessed 17 December, 2022] Available at <http://www.ilo.org/>
 45. Iliyasu Z, Galadanci HS, Muhammad A, Iliyasu BZ, Umar AA, Aliyu MH. Correlates of human papillomavirus vaccine knowledge and acceptability among medical and allied health students in Northern Nigeria. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology (Lahore).* 2022;42(3):452-460. doi:10.1080/01443615.2021.1910639
 46. Ampofo AG, Boyes AW, Asibey SO, Oldmeadow C, Mackenzie LJ. Prevalence and correlates of modifiable risk factors for cervical cancer and HPV infection among senior high school students in Ghana: a latent class analysis. *BMC Public Health.* 2023;23(1):1-12. doi:10.1186/s12889-022-14908-w
 47. Ajayi AI, Ismail KO, Akpan W. Factors associated with consistent condom use: A cross-sectional survey of two Nigerian universities. *BMC Public Health.* 2019;19(1):1-11.

doi:10.1186/s12889-019-7543-1

48. Chibianotu Ojimah OM. Awareness and uptake of human papillomavirus vaccines among female undergraduate students: Implications for cervical cancer prevention in South-South, Nigeria. *Port Harcourt Med J.* 2017;11(3):134-140. doi:10.4103/phmj.phmj
49. Izudi J, Okello G, Semakula D, Bajunirwe F. Low condom use at the last sexual intercourse among university students in sub-Saharan Africa: Evidence from a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One.* 2022;17(8 August). doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0272692
50. Kanmodi K, Chidiebere O, Nwafor N, Amoo B. Knowledge of HPV, HPV-induced cancers, and HPV vaccine among university students in medical laboratory science disciplines: Nigerian study. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology.* 2020;3(1):10-16. doi:10.5114/jogi.2020.94420
51. Adejuyigbe FF, Balogun BR, Sekoni AO, Adegbola AA. Cervical cancer and human papilloma virus knowledge and acceptance of vaccination among medical students in Southwest Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health.* 2015;19(1):140-148.

APPENDIX I

QUESTIONNAIRE

HUMAN PAPILOMAVIRUS INFECTION AND VACCINATION: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE AMONG FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES OF THE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN

Dear Respondent,

I am a 600L medical student carrying out a one-year project which is designed to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding HPV infection and vaccination. Kindly give your true opinion about each statement. Your opinion will be treated with utmost confidentiality. You are not required to include your name.

Thanks for your cooperation. Please tick [] where appropriate.

Accept [] Decline []

SECTION A: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

1. Age last birthday: _____ years
2. Marital status: Single [] Married []
3. Religion: Christian [] Muslim [] ATR [] Others _____
4. Tribe: _____
5. Course of study: _____
6. Class: 200L [] 300L [] 400L []
7. Level of education completed by father: No formal education [] Primary []
Secondary [] Tertiary []
8. Father's occupation: _____
9. Level of education completed by mother: No formal education [] Primary []
Secondary [] Tertiary []
10. Mother's occupation: _____
11. Average monthly allowance of the respondent: _____

SECTION B: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE REGARDING HPV INFECTION

12. Have you heard of human papillomavirus (HPV)? Yes [] No []

13. If yes, what was your source of information? School lectures [] Television/Radio [] Social media/Internet [] Family [] Friends [] Healthcare workers [] Religious organization [] Others (specify)_____ [You can choose more than one option]
14. What type of infection is HPV? Viral [] Bacterial [] Fungal [] Protozoan [] I don't know []
15. What is the mode of transmission of HPV? Faeco-oral [] Sexual intercourse [] Inhalational [] I don't know []
16. HPV causes: Genital warts [] HIV [] Oral cancer [] Cervical cancer [] Penile cancer [] I don't know []
17. HPV infects: Males only [] Females only [] Both []
18. Risk factors for HPV infection include: Early age at first sexual intercourse [] Obesity [] Smoking [] Multiple sexual partners [] I don't know []
19. Can one transmit HPV to their partners even without signs and symptoms of HPV infection? Yes [] No [] I don't know []
20. Have you had vaginal intercourse in the past four weeks? Yes [] No []
21. How old were you at your first sexual intercourse? _____ (age in years)
22. How many sexual partners (total number, with and without consent) have you had since your first sexual intercourse: _____
23. Have you ever used a condom? Yes [] No []
24. Did you use a condom the last time you had sex? Yes [] No []
25. In the last six months, how many times have you had sex? _____
26. In the last six months, how many times have you used condom while having sexual intercourse?

SECTION C: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND UPTAKE REGARDING HPV VACCINE

27. Have you heard of HPV vaccine? Yes [] No []
28. If yes, what is your source of information? Television/Radio [] Social media/Internet [] Family/Friends [] Healthcare workers [] Religious organization [] Others (specify)_____ [You can choose more than one option]
29. What diseases can be prevented using HPV vaccine? Cervical cancer [] Genital warts [] Genital herpes [] I don't know [] (You can choose more than one option)
30. Which gender should be vaccinated? Males only [] Females only [] Both [] I don't know []

31. When is the ideal period to commence vaccination? Before first sexual intercourse [] After first sexual intercourse [] I don't know []
32. Is the vaccine available in Nigeria? Yes [] No [] I don't know []
33. Do you know where to obtain HPV vaccine in your environment? Yes [] No []
34. How many doses of the vaccine is enough to confer immunity against the virus? 1 [] 2 [] I don't know []
35. How much does it cost to get vaccinated? _____ (amount in Naira)
36. Have you received HPV vaccine before? Yes [] No []
37. If you have received the vaccine, how many doses did you receive? _____
38. If you have received the vaccine, where did you receive it? _____

TABLE 1. ATTITUDE TOWARDS HPV VACCINATION

Statements	Disagree	Undecided	Agree
39. HPV vaccine is effective in preventing cervical cancer			
40. I will take the vaccine because I feel at risk of getting HPV infection			
41. I feel it is better to be vaccinated before becoming sexually active			
42. The cost of the vaccine discourages me from getting vaccinated			
43. I will use the vaccine if it is available in the health center to students at subsidized price			
44. I feel only sexually active ladies should get the vaccine			
45. HPV vaccine may have long term negative effects			
46. More information on HPV and its vaccine would be needed before I take the vaccine			
47. HPV vaccination should be included in the national program for immunization schedule			

SECTION D: REASONS FOR VACCINATION STATUS

48. If you have received HPV vaccine, why? Parent's recommendation [] Health worker's recommendation [] Friend's recommendation [] Personal decision [] Others: _____ (You can choose more than one option)
49. If you have not received HPV vaccine, why? Lack of awareness [] It is not affordable [] Don't know where to obtain the vaccine [] Don't know or uncertain about usefulness of the vaccine [] Fear of side effect [] Never considered it [] Religious reasons [] Others: _____ (You can choose more than one option.)

APPENDIX II

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

RESEARCH TITLE: HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS INFECTION AND VACCINATION: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE AMONG FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES OF THE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN

NAME AND AFFILIATION OF INVESTIGATORS

Samson Momoh (samson.momoh@med.uniben.edu)

Chidinma Ndubuisi (chidinmandubuisi001@gmail.com)

Department of Community Health,

University of Benin Teaching Hospital,

PMB 1111

Benin City, Edo State.

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

This study aims to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice regarding HPV infection and vaccination. To determine the reasons for HPV vaccination status among female undergraduate of the University of Benin.

PROCEDURES INVOLVED IN THE STUDY

In this study, questions will be asked regarding HPV infection, vaccination and reasons for vaccination will be asked.

CONFIDENTIALITY

All data collected will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Participants who volunteer to take part in the study will be given a unique study number and data will be collected without including the names of participants. Participants' information will be stored safely, secured by codes in computers using only the study identification number. All those handling data will not at any time reveal the participants' identity.

FINANCIAL COMPENSATION

There shall be no payment for participating in this study.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary and if you desire to withdraw out of this study at any time, punitive measures will be meted out against you on account of your withdrawal. Your refusal to participate or withdrawal from the study will not involve any negative consequences or loss of benefit to which you are otherwise entitled to.

RISK

It is not expected that any harm will come to you because of your participation in this study. The study does not entail any activity that would result in harm to you.

BENEFIT

The study will help assess the knowledge, attitude and practice regarding HPV infection and vaccination. It will provide us information that will be useful in increasing awareness and uptake of HPV vaccination.

FINANCIAL SPONSORSHIP

This research was self-sponsored.

The under listed may be contacted in case you have clarifications to make:

Samson Momoh (08131832460)

Chidinma Ndubuisi (07062558696)

Department of Community Health,

University of Benin Teaching Hospital.

PMB 1111

Benin City, Edo State.

If you have agreed to be a part of this study, please sign below. Thank you.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

**UNIVERSITY OF BENIN
TEACHING HOSPITAL**

P.M.B. 1111 BENIN CITY NIGERIA

Telephone: 052-600418

Telex: 41120 NG

Website: ubth.org

CHAIRMAN, BOARD OF MANAGEMENT:

CHIEF ADEDOJA ADEWOLU, MFR

CHIEF MEDICAL DIRECTOR:

PROF. DARLINGTON E. OBASEKI

MBBS (Benin), FMCPath
E-mail: darlobaseki@gmail.com

DIRECTOR OF ADMINISTRATION:

M.O. JIMOH-KADIR

B. Sc. (Hons)FJPM, Dip. Theo. AHAN

**HEALTH RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE
APPROVAL**

PROTOCOL NUMBER: ADM/E 22/A/VOL. VII/1483138

PROPOSAL TITLE: "HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS INFECTION AND VACCINATION: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE AMONG FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES OF THE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN"

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR(S): SAMSON AZIEGBEMIHIN MOMOH CHIDINMA NDUBUISI

DEPARTMENT/INSTITUTION: DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNITY HEALTH COLLEGE OF MEDICINE
UNIVERSITY OF BENIN TEACHING HOSPITAL, BENIN CITY, EDO
STATE, NIGERIA

DATE CONSIDERED FEBRUARY 9TH, 2023

DECISION OF THE COMMITTEE: APPROVED

THIS APPROVAL DATES 9/02/2023 TO 8/02/2024. IF THERE IS DELAY IN STARTING THE RESEARCH, PLEASE INFORM THE HREC SO THAT THE DATES OF APPROVAL CAN BE ADJUSTED ACCORDINGLY

REMARK:

CHAIRMAN: PROF. (MRS) A.N. OFILI

SIGNATURE & DATE: 9/02/2023

SUPERVISOR (S): PROF. OMOKHOA ADELEYE

DECLARATION BY INVESTIGATOR(S):

PROTOCOL NUMBER (please quote in all enquiries)

Note that no participant accrual or activity related to this research may be conducted outside of these dates and **you are to furnish the committee with the research activities at the completion of the study.** All informed consent forms used in this study must carry the HREC assigned number and duration of HREC approval of the study. In multiyear research, endeavor to submit your annual report to the HREC early in order to obtain renewal of your approval and avoid disruption of your research. No changes are permitted in the research without prior approval by the HREC except in circumstances outlined in the Code. The HREC reserves the right to conduct compliance visit your research site without previous notification

Signature & Date: 29/3/2023